

DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM FOR THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TPC	Technical Project Coordinator
[D]TWG	[Digital] Technical Working Group*/ Renamed Digital Focus Group after project amendment
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, engagement, sustainability, inclusion, aesthetics, digital impact, social good

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Executive Summary

This document outlines the Early Adopters Network for national and regional adoption of the digiNEB project. It defines Early Adopters as stakeholders who have actively and positively engaged with digital strategies in conjunction with NEB projects and NEB-aligned initiatives. A total of **134 Early Adopters** have been successfully onboarded, exceeding the original targets (KPI: 100). These individuals have become champions for the project, actively contributing to the promotion of NEB principles, educational methodologies and digital tools compiled by the project.

With the project's aim to join NEB and smart digital communities, the NEB@CERN 3-day event was achieved as an **early milestone, 4 months earlier than planned**, to bring together NEB and smart communities thought leaders and stakeholders around future directions for learning, digital and strategies for EU regions. As a high-level co-creation series of Think and Do Tanks, it provided recommendations for establishing the future NEB Academy, Thematic Working Groups (now Digital Focus Groups), and the Regional Innovation Model Handbook. The NEB Academy was a key theme at NEB@CERN, where dedicated sessions brought together key stakeholders to explore interdisciplinary approaches to education, sustainability, and digital integration in the construction industry. Several new collaborations started as a result of synergies between the NEB and digital communities.

Following this early milestone, **three notable channels for onboarding stakeholders were identified: 1) through the NEB Academy, 2) interaction with the digital and 3) the EU regions.**

The **NEB Academy onboarding** that started at NEB@CERN laid the groundwork for further development, continuing in a workshop at the University of Primorska, and culminating in the **formation of a new NEBA consortium** for the Horizon Europe open call. Subsequent developments included a workshop led by InnovaWood and EAAE, hosted at the InnoRenew CoE in Slovenia. The collaboration engaged key digiNEB partners, integrating expertise from wood research, architectural education, and digital tools, culminating in the establishment of the NEBA CSA project. **NEB Concepts, a series of 59 modular podcast episodes** featuring key members of the NEB community and early adopters, are a contribution to NEB Academy pedagogical resources from the digiNEB project.

As part of the **digital channel onboarding strategy** in the second part of the project, the JUST Industry Data Week, colocated with the JUST Data Annotation project at Linköping Science Park, successfully **onboarded communities from EDIH and industrial domains** working with digital technologies to integrate JUST Data practices for social good. It included keynotes and sessions on ethical data and data literacy, and the AI for Social Good: JUST Living Environments day dedicated to furthering the digiNEB digital agenda, which highlighted the potential of interdisciplinary collaboration in developing data-driven solutions to challenges such as urban soundscapes and sustainable living environments. The week featured discussions on key topics such as circularity, cognitive cities, and AI applications for social good, demonstrating the **integration of NEB principles with cutting-edge digital technologies.**

The **EU Regions onboarding channel** includes a long list of activities and events organised by the digiNEB community and members of the digiNEB EAB that involved onboarding regional NEB stakeholders and policymakers. The full list of events is available in the Annex of D3.3. Several components of a regional innovation strategy have been developed following the early successes of galvanising policymakers around NEB implementations across the EU regions. These have included the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook and The Regional Innovation Model for ecosystemic approaches to regional innovation, outlined in the RIM Handbook, which **leverages best practices from the NEB activities to align localised actions with broader regional and national strategies.** These efforts aim to create ecosystems

that address pressing environmental and social challenges and empower local communities to actively participate in co-creation processes.

The online strategy for early adoption has been revised to **focus more on substantial and enduring video content** rather than relying on the more ephemeral nature of social media posts. This has resulted in a significant increase in genuine engagement within the community. Presentations, keynotes and highlights from events such as NEB@CERN and the JUST Industry Data Week have provided a vehicle for engagement and adoption, knowledge transfer, and education. A total of **83 videos have been produced** (KPI: 24), garnering **over 1600 views** to date (KPI: 1000), while rising numbers will be updated in D5.4. There have been **223 social media posts** featuring Early Adopters' content (KPI: 192), and **11 online marketing campaigns** (KPI: 6).

The results from these onboarding activities provide a strong foundation for the **upcoming final event** and launch of the RIM Handbook at Architecture House in Brussels, where further dissemination and alignment of efforts through the network of project champions will maximise the impact of digiNEB across Europe.

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1. Introduction

Upon instruction by the President von der Leyen's NEB Advisor Ruth Reichstein, the Champions Network has been renamed 'the Early Adopter Network'.

We define a digiNEB 'Early Adopter' as a stakeholder who has actively and positively engaged with digital strategies for NEB projects, Smart Communities or NEB-aligned initiatives. These Early Adopters differ from traditional "users" in that they not only adopt these strategies but also promote them among their peers, providing critical feedback and expert insights to further refine and improve their implementation.

This updated deliverable outlines the Early Adopter Network's purpose, its engagement strategies, and the ongoing communication efforts designed to ensure comprehensive outreach across the EU regions. The document also presents an account of the achievements and lessons learned during the project's implementation.

Our efforts have focused on creating a robust network of Early Adopters by identifying key stakeholders and facilitating connections with national and regional initiatives. These activities leverage the resources and partnerships of the NEB External Advisory Group (EAG), NEB Partners, NEB High-Level Round Table (HLRT), and Friends of NEB. They also engage networks such as Interreg Europe, Cohesion Fund managers, and the European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE). The onboarding strategies aim to highlight success stories and best practices, with dissemination activities supported by a dynamic digital platform (digiNEB.eu), press releases, newsletters, and webinars showcasing Early Adopter achievements.

A key milestone was achieved ahead of schedule with the NEB@CERN event, held at the end of Month 5 instead of Month 9, which brought together NEB thought leaders, Smart Communities, and other critical stakeholders. This event set the foundation for the development of three major channels to Early Adoption, which are detailed in this deliverable:

1. **ACADEMIC** - NEB Academy and educational initiatives.
2. **DIGITAL** - engagement with EDIH and industry.
3. **REGIONAL** - onboarding of representatives of regional governments and communities.

These paths form the basis for this deliverable, which documents progress in each area and outlines future directions. It also presents the successes in onboarding early adopters via web and social media channels.

2. Early milestone joining the communities of NEB and Digital

2.1. Planning: Early adopter curation

This strategy focused on onboarding Early Adopters via in-person interaction. The first large-scale in-person interaction, NEB@CERN, was conceived as a high-level co-creation lab focusing on digitally-enabled approaches to sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics. The event was hosted by CERN IdeaSquare, who focus on methodologies for experimental innovation and learning through doing. CERN has also launched the CERN Green Village where they offer residencies to EU projects engaged with the Green Deal.

The event was curated by Michela Magas, Member of President von der Leyen's [High Level Round Table for the New European Bauhaus](#), Member of the Advisory Board of CERN ISAB-G.

2.1.1. Developing an Early Adopter Network

In order to create an Early Adopter Network, we first **identified several gaps in community interaction**, both within NEB and Smart Communities.

NEB has funded six Lighthouse projects. From their launch to the date of the NEB@CERN event in M5, these projects did not have the opportunity to collaborate and leverage synergies:

- **CULTUURCAMPUS:** A sustainable hub of arts, research, learning and community as a catalyst. By blending education, research, policy, and culture and considering the lived experiences of its residents, Cultuurcampus aims to transform the disadvantaged urban area of Rotterdam South (NL). The Cultuurcampus is in a historic building and acts as a hub for different groups and activities. (<https://www.cultuurencampusrotterdam.nl/en>)
- **NEB-STAR** (New European Bauhaus STAvangeR): NEB-STAR showcases how territorial transformation plans can incorporate the principles and values of the NEB in Stavanger (NO), Prague (CZ) and Utrecht (NL). The project tackles four emblematic challenges linked to climate-neutral cities, all considering local needs and concerns through co-creation with residents and stakeholders. (<https://nebstar.eu>)
- **NEBourhoods:** NEBourhoods prepares Munich-Neuperlach (DE) for the future as mapped out by the [European Green Deal](#) regarding the built environment, circularity, mobility, energy, food, and health. The project builds on the area's strengths – a strong sense of community, vast green areas, and large-scale housing, even if in need of renovation – and addresses its weaknesses – higher than average unemployment and lower than average education levels. (<https://www.nebourhoods.de>)
- **DESIRE** (Designing the Irresistible Circular Society): the project tackles the major challenges faced by societies and cities: climate change, biodiversity loss and resource challenges. Based on three main themes of inclusivity, circularity and reconciling cities with nature, the project uses art, architecture, and design to explore alternative ways of transforming territories across different European cities in Denmark, the Netherlands, Italy, Latvia and Slovenia. (<https://www.irresistiblecircularsociety.eu>)
- **EHHUR** (EYES HEARTS HANDS Urban Revolution): the project supports cities and vulnerable residents in transforming their built environment. Spread across seven different locations in the EU and Associated Countries (Denmark, Belgium, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Croatia), it

will seek to tackle socioeconomic and cultural challenges such as social segregation, energy poverty, and degradation of depopulated historical centres. (<https://eyesheartshands.eu/>)

- **Bauhaus of the Seas Sails:** the project aims to promote renewed ethical and aesthetic regenerative development from a diverse range of dimensions of our continued relationship with the sea. Conceived as a journey with Portugal as a starting point, the Bauhaus of the Seas will generate a design movement extending to all European coastal and maritime regions. (<https://bauhaus-seas.eu>)

NEB Lab Projects

Newly-funded NEB Projects had never interacted with the NEB Labs established in the first two years of the initiative, including:

- [NEB Goes South](#)
- the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#)
- [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#)
- the [Friends of NEB](#)
- the [NEB High Level Round Table](#)

Smart Communities

NEB projects had never interacted with the Smart Communities and Smart Cities projects such as:

- [DS4SSCC](#) (Data Space for Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities) is an EU-funded initiative that prepares for the creation of a data space for smart communities as an enabler of the EU Green Deal goals and Sustainable Development Goals.
- [Living in EU:](#) through co-creation with citizens, the project aims to bring the economic and social benefits of this transformation to all local communities and implement an inclusive digital Europe with powerful digital services, technologies, infrastructures and skills).
- [AURORAL:](#) Architecture for Unified Regional and Open digital ecosystems for Smart Communities and Rural Areas Large scale applications.
- [DUET:](#) Virtual city replicas that make it easy to understand the complex interrelation between traffic, air quality, noise and other urban factors. Powerful analytics model the expected impacts of potential change to aid evidence-based operational decisions and longer-term policy choices.
- [CommunityCity:](#) A transformative citizen-centred project that will launch 100 tech pilots addressing the needs of cities and communities through co-creation and co-learning processes.
- [CrAft:](#) Part of the New European Bauhaus initiative that places the transition to climate neutrality at the heart of urban stakeholders. The project supports the Mission Board on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the NetZeroCities platform in designing and deploying Climate City Contracts based on knowledge from CrAft's 3 Sandbox Cities (Bologna, Prague, and Amsterdam) and 60 CrAft Reference Cities.

digiNEB External Advisory Group

The digiNEB EAG, including members of the NEB HLRT, had never had a chance to collaborate with the NEB Lighthouses or identify synergies with Smart Communities. These include esteemed members of the digiNEB EAG:

- **Matti Kuittinen**, a representative of the Finnish Ministry of the Environment and Chair of the Nordic Carbon-Neutral Bauhaus;
- **José Pedro Sousa**, Professor at FAUP, University of Porto, co-founder of Bauhaus Goes South;
- **Mia Roth-Čerina**, Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Architecture at the University of Zagreb, co-founder of Bauhaus Goes South;
- **Tom Minderhoud**, Partner at UN Studio

CERN participation

Several CERN Green, Sustainable and Community initiatives have never had the chance to interact with the NEB Community or the Smart Communities, including:

- **CERN Green Village:** The Site and Civil Engineering (SCE) Department manages and develops CERN's real estate assets and infrastructures in agreement with CERN's scientific strategy, as well as all the services related to the caretaking and operation of the CERN site. Its vision is to create an inspiring and welcoming environment for CERN's scientific community now and in the future. With this vision in mind it has launched projects on sustainable design, construction & operation that aim to reduce gas & electricity consumption on campus operations by 5%, increase the positive impact on CERN's community & the environment, and create a Green Village within the CERN Campus where breakthrough technologies for sustainability can be tested. The CERN Green Village offers an agile and flexible village-size laboratory, an ideation and experimentation space, a platform for engagement with young innovators, and a showcase for innovation and societal engagement.
- **CERN IdeaSquare:** IdeaSquare aligns with and supports CERN's mission. Its specific focus is on offering a platform for early-stage collaboration between students, scientists, other CERN personnel and relevant organisations across disciplines. IdeaSquare raises interest in CERN beyond the purely scientific discovery. The activities carried out at IdeaSquare tie science innovation to SDGs and to a better future of our society. 12 activities intervene at the early stage of the innovation chain — what is known as the Fuzzy Front End of the R&D&I process. The processes we propose and develop trigger transformations in the way we think about societal challenges and prompt us to identify solutions that will have a real impact on people's lives. IdeaSquare raises interest in CERN beyond the purely scientific discovery. The activities carried out at IdeaSquare tie science innovation to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and work towards laying out a better future for our society.

NEB@CERN aimed to address these gaps by hosting a 2.5-day, in-person knowledge exchange workshop that brought together a diverse group of stakeholders. The event centred on a series of discussions and **Think and Do tanks**, which focused on the three main channels of early adopter onboarding: academic, digital, and regional. These sessions provided a platform for participants to exchange ideas, identify synergies, and collaboratively explore strategies to advance early adoption within their respective domains.

2.1.2. Securing Stakeholder Engagement

Resource management strategy

The need for such a large community event, matched with the limited project budget, required collaboration and colocation with strategic project partners. digiNEB funds focused on delivery of content in line with the DoA and community synergies. A collaborative effort resulted in **match funding** from:

- A globally relevant, authoritative scientific research host venue
- Individually-funded community projects from NEB and Smart Communities
- digiNEB funds for partner and EAG travel

Community management strategy

Event curator Michela Magas conducted community management in close collaboration with CERN. The following **strategies for securing engagement** were deployed:

- The event was curated as a high-level meeting limited to 50 participants on an invitation-only basis.
- Invitations were to project leaders and influencers representing broader digital and NEB communities.
- Individual meetings with each invited stakeholder to discuss their priorities with respect to NEB and digital.
- Special invitations were issued by CERN for those who required an official invitation, including EU officials.
- Individual scheduling and design of topics for discussion based on participants' and project priorities.
- Correspondence and briefing regarding the new NEB directions: NEB Academy and NEB and digital.
- Catering to individual needs, with special arrangements for accommodation at the CERN Hostel for low project budgets.
- Full catering including care of dietary requirements was provided by CERN.

2.1.3. Identifying synergies with NEB

By aligning individual and project priorities through curation, programming and facilitation of the in-person event, it was possible to group and engage the stakeholders in joint missions that reflect and advance the NEB priorities.

Synergies were identified between:

- NEB projects and Smart Communities
- NEB Lighthouse project missions and ambitions for the use of digital tools
- NEB Academy and the use of digital tools
- Individual NEB stakeholders (e.g.: Lighthouse project leaders, EAG members, Smart Communities projects) through the use of digital tools
- CERN project development and NEB project development

2.1.4. Designing KPIs for Early Adopter Engagement

For the successful onboarding of Early Adopters we set out several goals:

- **KPI 1:** Identify at least three major gaps in community interaction between NEB and Smart Communities.
- **KPI 2:** Identify at least three potential synergies that could arise from collaboration between digital and NEB community stakeholders
- **KPI 3:** Onboard at least 25 Early Adopters in the first six months of the project.
- **KPI 4:** Engage Early Adopters in at least one collaborative NEB-related activity resulting from in-person interaction at the first digiNEB Early Adopter event.

Figure 1: NEB@CERN multidisciplinary community

2.2. Action: First Early Adopter in-person event

The event was planned to run for 2.5 days starting on the afternoon of Monday 27th February. It combined inspirational talks with ‘think and do tanks’ – co-creation sessions focusing on the topics that included the new NEB Academy for a sustainable built environment, multidisciplinary Smart Communities, and digitally enabled beyond-human ecosystems. All participants were actively engaged in the co-creation process.

Figure 2: NEB@CERN presentation by Jan Bunge

2.2.1. Schedule

Monday, 27 February

12:00 → 13:00: Welcome, registration, sandwich lunch & mingling

13:00 → 14:00: Introduction to CERN, IdeaSquare, Green Village; NEB, Academy, digiNEB

Speakers:

Mar Capeáns Garrido, CERN Green Village

Markus Nordberg, CERN IdeaSquare

Ruth Reichstein, New European Bauhaus, European Commission

Franklin van der Hoeven, Director of Research of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and programme manager Open Science at TU Delft and Coordinator, digiNEB

Silvana Muscella, CEO Trust-IT and Technical Manager, digiNEB

Michela Magas, NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisory Board CERN ISAB-g

14:00 → 16:00: First “think and do” session on shaping the NEB Academy lead by the Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus with participation by ALL.

Introduction by **Ruth Schagemann**, President, Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE)

Moderators:

Matti Kuittinen, Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland

Helena Bjarnegård, Swedish National Architect, Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning (remotely)

16:00 → 16:30: Coffee Break

16:30 → 18:30: Second “think and do” session on shaping the NEB Academy lead by Bauhaus Goes South with participation by ALL.

Introduction by **Oya Atalay Franck**, President, European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE)

Moderators:

Mia Roth-Čerina, Council Member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Vice-Dean for International Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb

José Pedro Sousa, Member of the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Associate Professor at Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), University Of Porto

18:30 → 19:00: Free Time

19:00 → 22:20: Dinner (CERN Restaurant 2)

Tuesday, 28 February

09:00 → 09:30: Coffee Break

09:30 → 10:30: Meet the New European Bauhaus Lighthouse projects

Speakers:

Markus Reymann, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice

Nicole Arthur Cabrera, Bauhaus of the Seas and TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice

Dirk Ahlers, NEB-STAR and Senior Researcher and Project Manager +CityxChange at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

Heather Bergsland, NEB-STAR and Project Leader, New European Bauhaus Stavanger

Amanda Brandellero, CULTUURCAMPUS and Associate Professor, Erasmus University Rotterdam

Martin Luce, NEBourhoods and Director, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich

Aase Højlund Nielsen, DESIRE and Project Manager, BLOXHUB

Carlo Battisti, Eyes Hearts Hands and President, Living Future Europe
10:30 → 12:30: Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

10:30 → 12:30: Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

Introduction by **Michela Magas**, NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisor to CERN ISAB-g

Moderators:

Jan Åman, Author Duved and Norrlands Model

Florence Kuijl, Communication Manager, InnovaWood

Anna Sandak, leader in Wood Modification at the InnoRenew CoE and Associate Professor at University of Primorska

12:30 → 14:00: Sandwich lunch 1h 30m

14:00 → 14:15: NEB and digital: Visualising and exploring CERN’s CAD data in 3D, Virtual Reality and Digital Twins

Speaker: Jurgen de Jonghe, CERN

During the afternoon the participants will be able to explore the CERN Accelerator and Detector Complex using VR

14:15 → 14:30 ATTRACT- European platform for breakthrough innovation

Speaker: Pablo Garcia Tello, CERN

14:30 → 15:00: The junction between NEB and digital: Smart Communities

Speakers: Sandra Vengadasalam (Max Planck Digital Library) and **René Ranger** (Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL))

15:00 → 16:00: Meet the Smart Communities projects

Facilitator: Davor Meersman (The Maximal Impact Foundation and ICF)

Speakers:

Tom Minderhoud, Architect and Associate Director, UN Studio

Andreas Rudenå, CEO, Paramountric, senior researcher BASAJAUN and digiNEB ICF

Anke Schluensen-Rico, The HuT Project and Scientific Coordinator, Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)

16:00 → 16:30: Coffee Break

Angel Navarro, MAtchUP and Mobility Program Officer, Las Naves

Natalie Samovich, CoFounder ResilientGroup / Chair WG Energy AIOTI

Gert de Tant, CEO - Sirius NV / CTO The Maximal Impact Foundation

19:00 → 22:30: Dinner (Restaurant 2)

Wednesday, 1 March

09:00 → 09:30: Coffee Break

09:30 → 12:30: Introducing Beyond Human Ecosystems

Facilitator: Markus Reymann, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice

Speakers:

Dan Hill, Director, Melbourne School of Design and Professor in Built Environment, Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning, University of Melbourne

Jan Bunge, Director, Squint/Opera and contributor New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table

Jan Åman, Author Duved and Norrlands Model, ICF

12:30 → 14:00: Sandwich lunch 1h 30m

14:00 → 16:30: NEB and digital: the EU Regions and CERN

Facilitator: Michela Magas

Speaker: Faezeh Abbasi, CERN

16:30 → 17:00: Coffee, Wrap Up, Conclusions

17:00 → 17:30: Bus transportation to the Airport

Figure 3: NEB@CERN participants

2.2.2. Participants

Name	Title / Project
NEB Flagships/Academy/digiNEB Advisory	
Ruth Reichstein	NEB Advisor to President von der Leyen I.D.E.A., European Commission
Matti Kuittinen	Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland
Helena Bjarnegård	Swedish National Architect, Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning
Ruth Schagemann	President, Architects' Council of Europe (ACE)
José Pedro Sousa	Member of the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Associate Professor at Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), University Of Porto
Mia Roth Čerina	Council Member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Vice-Dean for International Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb
Tom Minderhoud	Architect and Associate Director, UN Studio
Anna Sandak	Leader in Wood Modification at the InnoRenew CoE and Associate Professor at University of Primorsk
NEB Lab and Lighthouse Projects	
Oya Atalay Franck	President, European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE) and NEB Partner
Frank van der Hoeven	Director of Research of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and programme manager Open Science at TU Delft and Coordinator, digiNEB

Michela Magas	NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisory Board CERN ISAB-g
Uwe Kies	NEB partner Innovawood, digiNEB
Mar Muñoz Aparici	Architect, Lamardebe, PhD Candidate TU Delft, researcher Bauhaus Goes South and digiNEB
Florénce Kuijl	NEB partner Innovawood, digiNEB
Markus Reymann	Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice
Aase Højlund Nielsen	DESIRE and Project Manager, BLOXHUB
Amanda Brandellero	CULTUURCAMPUS and Associate Professor, Erasmus University Rotterdam
Carlo Battisti	Eyes Hearts Hands and President, Living Future Europe
Dan Hill	NEB Advisor and Director, Melbourne School of Design and Professor in Built Environment, Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning, University of Melbourne
Dirk Ahlers	NEB-STAR and Senior Researcher and Project Manager +CityxChange at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
Martin Luce	NEBourhoods and Director, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich
Heather Bergsland	NEB-STAR and Project Leader, New European Bauhaus Stavanger
Jan Åman	Author Duved and Norrlands Model and Senior Researcher, Industry Commons Foundation
Jan Bunge	Director, Squint/Opera and contributor New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table
Magnus Myrenberg	Partner Aalto Capital, Advisor Industry Commons Foundation
Nicole Arthur (Cabrera)	Bauhaus of the Seas and TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice
Smart Communities	
Natalie Samovich	CoFounder ResilientGroup / Chair WG Energy AIOTI
Sandra Vengadasalam	Co-founder Bloxberg and Deputy Manager, Max Planck Digital Library
René Ranger	Project Owner Digital Labs, Max Planck Society
Anke Schluensen-Rico	The HuT Project and Scientific Coordinator, Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)
Angel Navarro	MAthUP and Mobility Program Officer, Las Naves

Andreas Rudenå	CEO, Paramountric, Senior Researcher at Industry Commons Foundation, Senior Researcher BASAJAUN and digiNEB
Davor Meersman	Executive Chairman, The Maximal Impact Foundation (MIMPACT) and Smart Communities Advisory, Industry Commons Foundation
Gert De Tant	CEO - Sirius NV / CTO The Maximal Impact Foundation
CERN	
Mar Capeans	CERN Green Village, Head of the Site and Civil Engineering (SCE) department, Particle Physicist
Markus Nordberg	Head of Resources Development of the Development and Innovation Unit (IPT-DI), Coordinator of IdeaSquare
Jurgen de Jonghe	CERN Digital Twin of the Accelerator
Pablo Garcia Tello	Section Head of the Development of EU Projects & Initiatives
Faezeh Abbasi	Senior Fellow, CERN Green Village
Sonja Kleiner	GL, CERN Environmental Protection Group
Claudia Marcelloni	IdeaSquare Communications Officer
Romain Muller	EU Projects Officer
Tuuli Utriainen	Fellow, IdeaSquare
digiNEB Management/Production	
Silvana Muscella	CEO Trust-IT and Technical Manager, digiNEB
Deborah Habermacher	Industry Commons Foundation
Francisca Siza	Industry Commons Foundation
Maria Giuffrida	Trust-IT
Rita Giuffrida	Trust-IT
Claudio de Majo	Trust-IT

2.2.3. NEB Academy Sessions (Academic channel)

The establishment of the NEB Academy is a top priority of the NEB implementation stage. As a flagship initiative of the European Year of Skills, the New European Bauhaus launched the NEB Academy focusing on skills for the sustainable living environment.

The NEB Academy will provide a coherent and accessible set of online and offline training at the European scale and promote inter-regional exchange of skills and best practices. The training will be developed with stakeholders from the construction ecosystem and delivered by structures recognised as NEB Academy Hubs (e.g. universities, research centres, professional chambers) with learning materials managed from a

First “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The session was introduced with a speech by Ruth Schagemann, President of the Architects’ Council of Europe (ACE). Matti Kuitinen from the Ministry of the Environment of Finland designed and conducted the co-creation session with Helena Bjarnegård, Swedish National Architect representing the Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning.

NEB ACADEMY

The first challenge addressed the need to take NEB values into the learning process. Community feedback highlighted the need for diverse and unusual perspectives, new knowledge driven by interdisciplinarity, experience as a way to understand real values, grounding of projects in real experiences, and a **focus on shifting mindsets and behaviours**.

The second challenge asked how to enable a deeper and faster sustainability transition with the NEB Academy. The feedback was dominated by the active inclusion of diverse target groups in the education process. These included policymakers, regulators, role models, children, diverse cultures and global perspectives. Incentives included lowering the entry barrier, making the transition irresistible, raising awareness of beauty, rewarding sustainability, active engagement with democracy, adaptation and regeneration initiatives. The education pillars derived from the discussion were **'learning by doing', learning by prototyping solutions, ensuring diversity and including accessibility**.

Q3: What is the role of aesthetics in building new skills and mindsets?

The third challenge questioned the role of aesthetics in building new skills and mindsets. A redefinition of what is considered beautiful was requested, including finding beauty in the NEB values. Considerations of context, the time we live in, the market forces, the functions, the perception, and the unknown, both challenge and define the term of aesthetics. Opening up dialogue and creating a common ground help to define aesthetics. Considerations of diversity led to finding beauty in informal settlements and temporary structures, particularly with reference to the work by Shigeru Ban and Sheela Patel. **Experience-based aesthetics were linked to beauty that emanates out of a sense of community.**

The fourth challenge considered how to work effectively together on the NEB Academy considering its complex context. Embracing complexity was suggested by working with both nature and technology, using multidisciplinary approaches and finding common ground. This resulted in learning that is **mission-oriented, place-based, joining disciplines and working from the ground up.**

Second “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The second NEB Academy co-creation session was introduced with a speech by Oya Atalay Franck, President of the European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE). The session was designed and conducted by the Bauhaus Goes South founders Mia Roth-Čerina, Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, and Prof. José Pedro Sousa of the Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), at the University of Porto.

The discussion started by examining what were the knowledge areas required. It proceeded by investigating how content can reflect needs, crises and policies; where does education take place; who participates in education; and where and how can different actors come together. The discussion

Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy

The third NEB Academy co-creation session was introduced with a speech by Michela Magas, Member of the NEB High Level Round Table, followed by an introduction by Prof. Anna Sandak to the work of the first planned NEB Academy Hub at InnoRenew / University of Primorska, Slovenia. The session was facilitated by Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood), and Mar Muñoz Aparici (EAAE).

NEB ACADEMY

The session covered questions such as the most relevant topics for the NEB Academy; how to attract different stakeholder groups; how to encourage more learning about biomaterials for construction; how to overcome the language barrier; what contribution would make the NEB Academy more sustainable, beautiful and inclusive; and where will the NEB Academy be in 5 and in 10 years' time. Community feedback included in a set of recommendations:

- the introduction of protocols and tutorials for municipalities on how to structure projects;
- considerations of indoor and outdoor health;
- learning inter-cultural management;
- cross-discipline communication and interoperability;
- flagship projects to learn from;
- working with industry to prototype solutions at scale;
- learning by doing.

The session concluded that **NEB should be a global academy and instigate change at a global scale.**

Figure 4: Sandra Vengadasalam of the Max Planck Digital Library presents the Bloxberg decentralised technology

2.2.4. NEB and Digital (Digital channel)

The second day of the workshop was designed to incentivise interaction, collaboration and synergies between the newly funded NEB Lighthouse projects, NEB Lab initiatives, CERN and Smart Communities projects.

A total of 15 projects were presented on the day, each allowing for interaction and identification of synergies, and closing the gaps identified in Section 2. Community interaction resulted in several proposals for collaborations and novel ideas for the use of digital technologies in NEB initiatives. Ongoing collaborations have been initiated between digiNEB partners and community members.

Figure 5: Gert de Tant, CEO Sirus NV, on the key principles behind urban technology strategies

Jan A. Q on Bauhaus 1922 concept illustration (Walter Gropius)

we should not follow others but rather want to appropriate for the times. Shape of circle as an all-encompassing symbol. Frank

Simplicity and ease of how it can be understood, Jan A.

JAN A:

it is simple!

Gropius didn't have to see global challenges and needs: climate, democracy, Jan A.

if we don't figure out the problems we have in democracy, we are fucked, Jan A.

it requires new business models, we have to find a better mix of financial models, and then you can make research actually doing

We have to create synergies, participation; we have to address the topic of intellectual property, else it's not going to work

if we don't address democracy now, we are F*cked!

if we don't figure out the problems we have in democracy, we are fucked, Jan A.

We need to look at education, what can research be and how can it be applied to this much broader spectrum of things

NEB has to go global, else there is no point in doing this!

2.2.5. Recommendations for the EU Regions (Regional Channel)

The third day introduced ecosystemic approaches to the junction between NEB and digital, with keynotes by Dan Hill and Jan Bunge about built and virtual environments, and community facilitation and innovation by digiNEB Early Adopter Jan Åman, with particular focus on scaling best practice for the European Regions.

Recommendations were created for topics to be developed further in the followup event in Slovenia on 6-7 March, for activities in the EU Regions, and for further interaction of the NEB community with CERN. These included:

- linking all projects represented across the regions and creating a large ecosystem;
- engaging the NEB lighthouses in the creation of the NEB Academy and its ecosystem;
- creating a safe space to explore and prototype together;
- joining more artists and scientists to open up new knowledge;
- aligning local goals to have impact at large scale;
- empowering and incentivising local communities to engage in democratic processes;

What can we give to regional governments as guidelines/pointers to empower them to participate? (Q Michela)

All materials have been compiled and are accessible to the community, including community contact details (with permission), co-creation boards, presentations and media.

The feedback has been overwhelmingly positive. The following is a selection of feedback received in writing:

- *"Thanks again for very inspiring days at CERN!"*
- *"It was really astonishing to meet all these interesting people with the similar vision and values for the future, everybody from his/her angle. It really gave a lot of inspiration and thoughts on how to tackle the challenges of the future."*
- *"You managed to make the event both highly relevant, intense, inspiring and with an atmosphere of being part of something special. I brought back with me so much inspiration and so many new and relevant contacts – haven't been able to catch up with them all yet but for sure, it will have a positive influence on some parts of the (NEB Lighthouse) project."*
- *"I will take a lot of food for thought to other communities to share. And there have been very good unexpected encounters for me during these days."*
- *"Thousand thanks for this initiative and to have been/be part of it!"*

The main takeaways from the workshop have been summarised as follows:

- It is important that NEB Academy isn't just another course, but a unique learning method that validates the knowledge acquired from online curricula with regular hands-on, collaborative, cross-disciplinary, mission-driven creative labs focused on real impacts. It should enable knowledge sharing and become a frontrunner of practice- and place-based learning based on the principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics.

- Inclusion and accessibility in the living environment should feature prominently together with multiple notions of sustainability and diverse aesthetics.
- NEB Academy should include inter-regional exchange of skills & best practices and include specific skills for different regions.
- Systematic approach to identify existing gaps and needs of different target groups must be assured. Satellites of the NEB Academy or different hubs could have different main focuses that would complement each other and, in this way, assure a holistic approach to the green transition of the building sector.
- The governance structure of the NEB Academy and its operation should be able to adapt as hubs evolve. An Advisory Board should be included as part of the governance of the NEB Academy as it evolves.

2.3. Impacts and plans arising from the establishment of the Early Adopter Network

The NEB@CERN event achieved multiple, far reaching impacts, and set the parameters for further Early Adopter engagement.

2.3.1. Creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network

The event has enabled the creation of the digiNEB Early Adopter Network represented by a new hybrid community combining the digital and Smart Communities projects, NEB Lab and Lighthouse projects. This is a major Milestone for the digiNEB project and for European Commission NEB ambitions.

Individual links and synergies have been developed among the hybrid community members and further introductions to other potential Early Adopters followed. The project leaders and influencers represented at the event are now in the position to onboard their communities of stakeholders and extend the Early Adopter Network.

2.3.2. Early Adopters Network co-author the digiNEB White Paper

Members of the newly established network suggested to collaborate on a White Paper relevant both for NEB and Smart Communities. The following initial topics have been suggested:

Mission-oriented learning

Learning that is not just based on best practice but joins knowledge from various disciplines to create sustainable solutions

Co-learning

- Multidisciplinary
- Trans-generational
- Public-private

Understanding value networks

- Closed-loop material lifecycles
- Keeping within the Donut Economy Model
- Digital systems for resilience and for responsibility

Design for beyond-human ecosystems

- Multi-species ecosystemic integration
- Strategies for ecosystem living
- Design for regional ecosystems framework conditions

The topics have been aligned with the Thematic Working Groups.

2.3.3. Regular in-person events by the NEB Lighthouse projects

The collocated event has physically galvanised all NEB projects and created a real community that wishes to collaborate from here on. NEB Lighthouses will now host the community regularly every few months. A schedule of monthly events hosted locally by individual NEB Lighthouse projects has been created in the Notion repository.

2.3.4. Collaboration between NEB and CERN

Member of CERN Management, Mar Capeans Garrido received an invitation to proceed on 'NEBifying CERN' by Ruth Reichstein. This creates the opportunity to create the first 'NEB Beacon' for the 'NEBification' of a large research facility.

For NEBifying CERN, the community proposed on the last day a week-long prototyping event at CERN outdoors in summer, that would test ideas for sustainable, community oriented environments, together with CERN stakeholders. This event could also validate some of the learning from the NEB Academy.

2.3.5. Thematic Working Groups

Inspired by the co-creation of the NEB Academy, the event has provided the setting for a proposal for a collaborative White Paper by the newly established community. How further activities are planned as part of the TWG onboarding strategies is detailed in the section below.

2.3.6. KPIs

As per the impacts listed under Section 2.3, with the first in-person event **all of our goals for onboarding Early Adopters, set in Section 2.1.4, have been exceeded**. In addition to meeting the ambitions of WP3, the first in-person cross-domain community event **achieved Milestone MS4.1 (due in Month 9) early in the beginning of Month 6 of the project** with the first engagement and co-creation between digital R&I stakeholders and the NEB communities of practice.

Achievements resulting from the first strategy of onboarding Early Adopters include:

- 30+ Early Adopters who are project leaders and community influencers ready to be added to the digiNEB website;
- EAG members fully engaged with Early Adoption through identified synergies and co-creation and White Paper;
- CERN management staff onboarded and collaborating with NEB;
- All agreed to have their details stored in the digiNEB platform hence large addition to the digiNEB community;
- Several followup community events are organised, hosted by the individual NEB lighthouses and NEB partners;

- Each Early Adopter leads a NEB or Smart Community linked to their lighthouse or flagship projects paving the way for further adoption.

3. Onboarding Channel: ACADEMIC

3.1. Route to the NEB Academy

On the 6th and 7th of March 2023, an invitation-only workshop was held at the InnoRenew CoE research centre in Izola, Slovenia, taking forward the development of the NEB Academy with focus on upskilling for bio-based materials, circularity and sustainability in construction.

Uwe Kies (InnovaWood) and Michela Magas (Industry Commons Foundation) were invited to contribute as NEB Partner and Member of the NEB High Level Round Table, and were able to continue the work initiated at the NEB@CERN event on behalf of the digiNEB consortium.

Figure 6: Participants in the invitation-only NEB Academy workshop on bio-based materials, circularity and sustainability in construction

Figure 6: Sketching solutions for the NEB Academy at the InnoRenew Workshop

The main takeaways from the workshop have been summarised as follows:

- It is important that NEB Academy isn't just another course, but a unique learning method that validates the knowledge acquired from online curricula with regular hands-on, collaborative, cross-disciplinary, mission-driven creative labs focused on real impacts. It should enable knowledge sharing and become a frontrunner of practice- and place-based learning based on the principles of sustainability, inclusion and aesthetics.
- Inclusion and accessibility in the living environment should feature prominently together with multiple notions of sustainability and diverse aesthetics.
- NEB Academy should include inter-regional exchange of skills & best practices and include specific skills for different regions.
- Systematic approach to identify existing gaps and needs of different target groups must be assured. Satellites of the NEB Academy or different hubs could have different main focuses that would complement each other and, in this way, assure a holistic approach to the green transition of the building sector.
- The governance structure of the NEB Academy and its operation should be able to adapt as hubs evolve. An Advisory Board should be included as part of the governance of the NEB Academy as it evolves.

3.2. Designing the NEB Academy Alliance

Following this first NEB Academy workshop, InnovaWood and the University of Primorska (Prof. Andreja Kutnar, member of the digiNEB EAB) initiated a new consortium for the open call [HORIZON-JU-CBE-2023-2-S-01](#). The full proposal was submitted on 4 Oct 2023 and accepted on 24 Nov 2023 with a score of 13 points. The “NEBA Alliance” consortium is coordinated by the University of Primorska, Slovenia, and includes 14 partners in 11 countries. It is a 2-year CSA of 1 million EUR running from 1 Apr 2024 until 31 March 2026 under [grant agreement 101160532](#).

digiNEB partners TU Delft, EAAE and InnovaWood were instrumental in the project design and are project members with key responsibilities:

- TU Delft is task leader of designing and setting up the pilot digital platform for educational content to be spread by the NEB Academy.
- EAAE is the main network partner to reach out to the EU architectural education community.
- InnovaWood is WP Comms leader and main network partner for the EU wood R&I community.

The collaboration of TU Delft, EAAE and IW initiated as nucleus under digiNEB could thus set the basis for a strategic partnership with a long-term perspective. Both the EU wood research and the architectural education communities have a mutual interest in creating bridges between their disciplines: wood construction is an emerging field which needs to expand into multi-storey buildings and urban planning of neighbourhoods and cities, and architecture must expand its knowledge into the area of biobased, sustainable materials such as wood and others.

Some notable highlights of digiNEB setting the ground for the NEB Academy:

- TU Delft is a leader in open education and open data science. Their expertise will make sure to guide the NEB Academy partners towards a platform solution that is fully aligned with the NEB

values and principles. This is already displayed in the first version of the NEB Academy website: <https://neb.academy/>

- A first dummy demonstrator of the NEBA platform concept was co-created under the digiNEB TWGs together with Nordic Bauhaus stakeholders RISE (Sweden), Aalto University (Finland) and Estonian Arts Academy (EKA, Estonia), who then also have joined the NEBA consortium to create the NEBA North Hub: <https://neb.academy/hubs>
- InnovaWood gave several talks about digiNEB and the emerging NEB Academy to stakeholders who helped to gain inputs for shaping the new consortium, for example to the EC Social Dialogue partners EFBWW, CEI-Bois and others at the RESILIENTWOOD conference in Zagreb, Croatia, on 7 Sep 2023: <https://zenodo.org/records/8325343>, <https://www.cei-bois.org/resilientwood>
- EAAE, InnovaWood and the European Bioeconomy University (EBU, chaired by BOKU University) are the founding partners of the NEB Academy Outreach Hub, which establishes a primary contact point for outreach to and coordination with other European projects, networks, initiatives, and key stakeholders in research, education, and policy through a jointly cosigned Memorandum of Understanding (MoU): <https://neb.academy/outreach>

3.3. Support to other NEB consortia

The digiNEB project activities and results have been used to inspire further NEB-related consortia. InnovaWood disseminated materials and key documents (including NEB Compass, NEB toolbox, NEB Labs, CrAft Cookbook, digiNEB early adopters collection and best practices databases, NEB Academy concept notes) to its membership and advised the coordinators who initiated new consortia for open calls under Horizon Europe. These activities informed and guided the following consortia:

Call Topic: [HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-02-03](#) - Solutions for the identification of vulnerable buildings and people-centric built environment, and for improving their resilience in disruptive events and altered conditions in a changing climate (Built4People Partnership)

- TiMBERED-Path, 16 partners, coordinated by IAAC, Spain

Call Topic: [ERASMUS-EDU-2024-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP](#) - Alliances for Education and Enterprises

- EBA - European Bioeconomy Academy, 20 partners, coordinated by ITA, Finland

Call Topic: [HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5](#) - Climate-smart use of wood in the construction sector to support the New European Bauhaus

- Circonium, 26 partners, coordinated by FCBA, France
- HoliWood, 19 partners, coordinated by CTFC, Spain
- LiveInWood, 17 partners, coordinated by CZU, Czech Republic
- WoodOPIA, 11 partners, coordinated by Tecnalía, Spain
- WoodStock, 13 partners, coordinated by University of Gent, Belgium

Note: The [WoodStock consortium \(grant no. 101181021\)](#) was selected for funding and was launched in November 2024. InnovaWood and TU Delft are partners active on research and stakeholder engagement, which will ensure that digiNEB results can be further capitalised on in this major NEB-inspired project for the wood sector.

3.4. NEB Concepts Modular Podcast as learning materials

Topic: Local and regional solutions

Aase Højlund Nielsen - Part 3
 Sustainability, Community engagement, Climate change and adaptation, Co-creation and participatory design, Human-centered design, Local and regional solutions

Andreja Kutnar - Part 5
 Sustainability, Climate change and adaptation, Education innovation, Policy-making and evaluation, Technology integration, Local and regional solutions

Jan Bunge - Part 3
 Systems thinking, Urban design and development, Sustainability, Lifecycle thinking and long-term planning, Ecosystem approach, Local and regional solutions

Markus Reymann - Part 2
 Community engagement, Interdisciplinary approach, Art and culture, Aesthetics, Local and regional solutions, Inclusion, Environmental conservation

Mia Roth-Cerina - Part 1
 Architectural education and practice, Sustainability, Inclusion, Local and regional solutions, Nature-based solutions, Cultural heritage and diversity

Roberto Cavallo - Part 2
 European collaboration and policy, Local and regional solutions, Knowledge sharing and dissemination, Cultural heritage and diversity, Education innovation, Interdisciplinary approach

Figure 8: Thematic search for learning topics in the NEB Concepts modular podcast

Designed as part of digiNEB’s contribution to the educational channel for onboarding early adopters, and packaged as a series of short pedagogical tools and learning materials, NEB Concepts features insightful conversations with leading architects, educators, and project leaders. The discussions deal with topics at the intersection of sustainability, innovation, and human-centred design. Students and educators have direct access to those leading members of the NEB Community shaping the future of urban development, cultural heritage, and community empowerment.

NEB Concepts allows to choose tags to explore themes such as climate adaptation, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration – or stick with the wide-ranging thoughts of a single interviewee. Each short episode provides a collection of ideas and practices, projects and reflections, highlighting the transformative potential of the New European Bauhaus for a more inclusive and sustainable future.

The interviewees

- **Aase Højlund Nielsen** - DESIRE and Project Manager, BLOXHUB
- **Andreja Kutnar** - Director at InnoRenew CoE
- **Davor Meersman** - CEO FutureCraft Habitats and Chairman FutureCraft Foundation
- **Francesca Rizzo** – Professor of Design at Politecnico di Milano, Rector’s Delegate for European Projects
- **Frank van der Hoeven** - Director of Research of the Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment and programme manager Open Science at TU Delft and Coordinator, digiNEB
- **Jan Bunge** - Director at Squint/Opera, Landscape Architect
- **Markus Reymann** - Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice
- **Matti Kuittinen** - Professor of resource-efficient construction at Aalto University’s Department of Architecture & Senior Specialist at the Finnish Ministry of the Environment
- **Mia Roth-Čerina** - Architect and Associate Professor at the Faculty of Architecture in Zagreb
- **Roberto Cavallo** - Architect/Founding Partner STUDIO-AI, Amsterdam; Associate Professor dept Architecture, Faculty of Architecture, TUDelft
- **Selma Harrington** - Co-director of the Union of International Architects EDUCOM and Chair of the ACE EU Projects work group. Founding principal of the New European Bauhaus Forum Bosnia and Herzegovina with Green Building Council.
- **Sheela Patel** - Director of SPARC, founder of National Slum Dwellers Federation of governments, bilateral and international agencies, foundations and other organisations, co-founder of Slum Dwellers International and co-founder of Roof Over Our Heads.

3.5. EAAE digiNEB workshop at CA²RE Conference in Valencia

Partners from EAAE organised the digiNEB workshop, *"Sharing Experimentation: New European Bauhaus and Digital Interplays – Experiences in Southern Europe"*, as part of the 15th CA²RE Academic Conference in Valencia on 12 April 2024. This hybrid session, organised under the digiNEB initiative, explored the dynamic interplay between the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and digital tools, with a particular focus on their application and impact in southern Europe, specifically Spain and Portugal.

The CA²RE Conference was part of an ongoing series of events organised by the Conferences for Artistic and Architectural Research. The network is dedicated to advancing the quality and evaluation of Design-Driven Research, which encompasses Research by Design, Artistic Research, Practice-Driven/-Based/-Led Research, and Creative Practice Research. The community aims to bridge gaps in knowledge across disciplines such as architecture, design, the arts, and environmental studies. CA²RE conferences bring together senior academics, advanced researchers, and early-career scholars to engage in peer reviews at critical stages of their work. The conferences focus on architectural and urban design, performing and visual arts, landscape architecture, and sustainable development.

The workshop brought together researchers, practitioners, and community stakeholders to examine how digital technologies and collaborations are reshaping the architectural and built environment landscapes in the region. It highlighted innovative projects and practices that connect the NEB's interdisciplinary ethos with the European Green Deal, showcasing examples of how digital ecosystems can foster sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics in design-driven research and practice.

Participants engaged in discussions about the transformative potential of digital tools in promoting innovation and addressing contemporary challenges within the built environment. The workshop emphasised the value of interdisciplinary collaboration and the integration of digital strategies to support the NEB's vision of creating sustainable, beautiful, and inclusive living spaces, contributing to a shared understanding of its impact in southern Europe.

The Valencia event was supported by ARENA (Architectural Research European Network Association), digiNEB partner EAAE (European Association for Architectural Education), and ELIA (European League of Institutes of the Arts). This edition placed significant emphasis on the intersection of design-driven research with societal challenges such as climate change, sociological issues, and spatial transformations.

It provided a platform for participants to critically evaluate and enhance the innovative and transformative potential of their research strategies.

Figure 9: digiNEB session at CA²RE conference in Valencia

Programme:

**Sharing Experimentation
New European Bauhaus and Digital
Interplays - Experiences in Southern Europe**

Speakers:

Linking the European Green Deal with aesthetics and inclusiveness - **Roberto Cavallo**
Council member EAAE & Associate Professor, Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment, Delft
University of Technology

Regional experimentation in the NEB: NEB Goes South - **Mia Roth-Čerina**
Council member EAAE & Professor Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb

Learning by living: advanced technologies supporting inclusive and regenerative education, design and
spaces - **Mathilde Marengo**
IAAC Head of Studies & MaCT Co-Director (Barcelona)

València, a city for experimentation - **Mar Ferrer Sáez**
Smart Cities, urban Innovation and sustainable development in Valencia Innovation Agency, municipality
of Valencia (Valencia)

digiNEB: connecting the digital with the built environment - **Frank van der Hoeven**
Director of Research, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment & Programme Manager
OpenScience, TU Delft

Figure 10: Participants in the digiNEB session at CA²RE conference in Valencia

4. Onboarding Channel: DIGITAL

4.1. CERN Follow-up Workshop: NEB Lighthouses and ICT

Following on from the success of the NEB@CERN event, CERN invited participants back to foster collaboration between ICT experts, NEB Lighthouses, and Labs. The Rebalance event took place over a full day of discussions and deliberations on September 25th, 2023, bringing together experts on Nature-based Solutions (NBS), the NEB community, and ICT specialists.

Participants from NEB projects DESIRE, BOSS, NEB Goes South, and digiNEB engaged in focused discussions, exploring innovative approaches to sustainability, digital transformation, and community-driven solutions. The workshop at CERN's IdeaSquare facility served to strengthen interdisciplinary connections and develop actionable strategies for addressing complex regional and urban challenges.

4.2. Onboarding via Thematic Working Groups / Digital Focus Groups

The digital thematic working groups, renamed digital focus groups after the project amendment, were conducted in order to identify gaps and trends in the NEB landscape, focusing on 4 ex-ante identified areas of interest. Onboarding was thus not a purposeful goal of the focus groups, but rather an adjacent one. The planning, organisation and execution of the technical digital working groups offered the opportunity to disseminate the activities and objectives of the DigiNEB project, as did participation in multiplier, connected or adjacent events and 1x1 interviews.

The recruitment of participants in the Technical Digital Working Group was based on initial desk research and snowball sampling. The aim was to allow for a broad geographical distribution, as well as diversity of perspectives, while keeping the DOA requirement of involving top experts in the discussions. For reaching the desired number of participants, an initial sample of 3 times the number of desired participants was planned for. As such, an average of 20 invitations were sent for each DTWG, from EU member states and associated countries. As mentioned in connected deliverables, other cross-recruitment strategies included disseminating the planned online focus groups in:

- the NEB newsletter through the European contact point for NEB;
- the European Commission's NEB community platform calendar of events;
- presentation given in the European Federation for Living Social Topic Group;
- the TU Delft AI initiative.

In addition to the 4 originally planned focus groups on the themes of Design & Architecture, Production & Construction, Verticals, Community & Sustainability, and aligning with current trends, an additional hybrid, two part technical group was conducted around the topic of AI in response to emerging disruptive trends during project implementation.

During the Technical Digital Working Groups, participants manifested their interest in the activities and objectives of the DigiNEB project, in the resources offered by the DigiNEB website and engaged in sustained debates around the addressed questions. Indicators of this are the facts that discussions surpassed the initially allocated time, that participants supplemented discussions by indicating additional resources related to the debated subjects and that participants inquired during the discussions on the moment that the research deliverables resulting from the technical digital working groups will be ready in order to access them. Participants in the TDWG also requested to be kept up to date with the results and follow up of the DigiNEB project, since it proved to be a linking pin to the current status of the broader New European Bauhaus Programme. Given this interest, all participants in the DTWG will receive the results of the DTWG and announcement of the final event and any follow-up activities.

The data collection activity dedicated to AI was embedded in a one week data intensive event. The detailed methodology, analysis and policy recommendations incorporating the results are detailed in Deliverables 2.5, 5.3 and associated research outputs. The embedding of the data collection dedicated to AI in the larger event facilitated participant engagement and group cohesion, input collection being facilitated by formal and informal interactions around broader subjects of data, technology and AI. This format was in line with the NEB principles: Beautiful, Sustainable, Together, engaging participants in the offline, online and hybrid approaches, accommodating different preferences. The content of the focus group discussions incorporated the perspective on the new NEB priorities and the Green Deal, and the human and value centric European approach AI, in the landmark year for the adoption of the AI Act.

4.2.1. Action: NEB Academy and thematic groups

Together with partner InnovaWood the digiNEB partners decided to focus the Thematic Working Group for 'production and construction' toward the newly established NEB Academy launched by President von der Leyen.

4.2.2. KPIs

The results of the TWG are embedded in the Landscape report and gap analysis (D. 2.5.) and Roadmap Report (5.3). The target of 4 TWGs has been achieved.

Figure 11: Lena Miranda, CEO of Linköping Science Park, welcomes digiNEB delegates to the AI For Social Good: JUST Living Environments day

4.3. Onboarding EDIH and Industry: JUST Industry Data Week

A key strategy for onboarding Early Adopters within the digital domain was to establish connections between digiNEB and the **European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), alongside leading industry players participating in the digital transformation.** To achieve this, the project aligned digiNEB's ecosystem with that of the Linköping Science Park EDIH, which provided access to a network of large organisations such as Ericsson and Actia Nordic, as well as innovative SMEs addressing societal challenges through data and technology. By colocating with the JUST Industry Data Week, digiNEB was able to integrate its community into broader conversations around AI for Social Good and JUST Data. The week-long event featured high-level participants from academia, industry, policy and the creative sectors, exploring practical and ethical applications of data in addressing societal challenges. The strategic placement of NEB topics such as JUST Living Environments, Models for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation, and Cognitive Cities within a context of data justice, Sound for Urban Environments and industry presentations revealed connections and synergies across domains that would form the bridge to new areas for the project and bring digital and industry actors firmly on board.

4.3.1. Securing Stakeholder Engagement

Resource management strategy

The need to onboard European Digital Innovation Hubs and industry working in the digital transformation, combined with the limited project budget, required collaboration and colocation with strategic project partners. digiNEB funds focused on delivery of content in line with the DoA. A collaborative effort resulted in a multi-way **match funding** from:

- A highly reputable science and business host venue at the Linköping Science Park EDIH providing access to 600+ relevant technology companies
- Support for participant travel from the City of Linköping recognised by the EC as the current EU Capital of Innovation
- Support for catering for the week by 5 Linköping Science Park companies.
- Colocation with Vinnova – Swedish Innovation Agency funded project JUST Data Annotation, with clearly defined colocation boundaries, providing access to additional relevant content
- digiNEB funds for digiNEB content delivery and production, partner and EAG travel.

Community management strategy

Event curator Michela Magas deployed the following **strategies for securing engagement** that would benefit the digiNEB project using colocated resources:

- Multiple meetings were organised with Linköping Science Park company CEOs and managers to discuss their priorities in advance of the event, and to onboard participation, including Ericsson, Actia Nordic, Combitech and several SMEs
- Multiple meetings were organised with the leaders of national industrial data labs who contributed to the event content across sectors including health, space, construction, mining, steel and railways.
- Individual meetings were held with digiNEB EAB to get advice on the content with respect to NEB and digital.
- Special invitations were issued by Lena Miranda, CEO of Linköping Science Park to members of Regional Governments.
- digiNEB components of the programme were co-curated with partner TU Delft, and positioned strategically together with industry keynotes to enable mutual exchanges.
- A dedicated digiNEB full day (10:00-19:00) was devoted to a priority topic of AI for Social Good, following the recent policy directives.
- Event catering including care of dietary requirements was organised to be provided by 5 partner companies.
- Visiting participation was secured by ensuring the cover of travel expenses from Visit Linköping.

4.3.2. Identifying synergies

The curation, programming and facilitation of the in-person event allowed for the identification of several synergies between digiNEB, business and industry.

Synergies were identified between:

- Data Ethics stakeholders: the digiNEB priorities of responsible uses of data (TU Delft and ICF) and the needs across industry sectors for the ethical management of data in industrial applications.

- Digital applications use case stakeholders: NEB methods for hands-on experimentation and testing of real-world applications and the needs of EDIH and industry to test data-driven solutions in real use case scenarios.
- Smart cities stakeholders: NEB community testing of the impact of data-driven systems on living environments and the sustainability needs of smart cities.
- Cross-domain stakeholders: multiple synergies were identified in collaboration across NEB and industrial domains.

4.3.3. Designing KPIs for Early Adopter Engagement

The following ambitions were set for the onboarding of Early Adopters:

- **KPI 1:** Bring digiNEB and EDIH/industry together in dedicated workshops around responsible use of data.
- **KPI 2:** Identify at least three potential synergies that could arise from collaboration between digiNEB and industry stakeholders.
- **KPI 3:** Onboard at least 30 Early Adopters from the interaction between NEB and EDIH/ industry.

Figure 12: Andrew Dubber interviews Elisabeth Sjöstrand, R&D Manager at Ericsson.

4.3.4. Event programming

JUST Industry Data Week took place from the 16th to the 21st of September 2024 at Linköping Science Park. While some of the week was in-person only, the full day of Inspirational Talks, the Global Brainstorming sessions, the AI Literacy Workshop and the full day dedicated to digiNEB: **AI for Social Good: JUST Living Environments** were hybrid, online and interactive.

DAY1: Monday 16th September, centred on cross-domain knowledge exchange, with keynote presentations, knowledge-sharing sessions, and discussions that addressed the challenges and opportunities of working with data across different industries.

The topics explored included data sovereignty, indoor air quality, design for healthcare, AI in industry, and the intersection of data and soundscapes in urban environments. The day concluded with an interactive session on sound for urban environments and a live interview with Ericsson’s R&D Manager, which set the stage for deeper engagement with practical and ethical issues in the days to come.

DAY 2: the day opened the event to the participation of a global audience, connecting participants through hybrid brainstorming sessions and provocations designed to spark interdisciplinary dialogue. The discussions addressed key topics such as data ethics, the challenges of training AI systems with diverse datasets, and the use of data for urban environments and satellite applications. These sessions provided a platform for global perspectives and emphasised the need for collaboration in addressing shared challenges across regions.

Figure 13: Ana Kuštrak Korper, PhD student of service design at Linköping University, working with Naveen Venkatesh Sridharan, PhD researcher of ICT for industrial systems at Luleå University of Technology.

DAY 3: the day focused on hands-on engagement through field trips and experimental activities within Linköping. Participants collected data from the local environment and began developing prototypes that incorporated insights from direct experience with urban soundscapes.

A data literacy workshop provided opportunities for participants to deepen their understanding of AI governance frameworks while engaging in creative data practices. Collaborative sound experimentation added a dynamic layer to the prototyping activities.

DAY 4: the day was dedicated to synthetic and health data, with presentations and workshops highlighting innovations in these areas. Contributions included explorations of synthetic data in machine learning models, data governance in health applications, and the role of knowledge graphs in integrating health data systems. The day also included a hands-on workshop on the relationship between metadata, ontology, and structured data, and concluded with a focus on applying these concepts to regional healthcare ecosystems.

DAY 5: dedicated entirely to digiNEB, the day centred on the application of data for social good, with a particular focus on urban and regional innovation. The morning sessions included reflections on ethical

data practices, participatory design, and ecosystemic approaches to regional development. The event also featured the launch of the digiNEB Handbook for EU Ecosystemic Regional Innovation and discussions on sustainable urban planning and cognitive cities. The day concluded with a showcase of the week's experiments, installations, and creative outputs, which brought together participants' work in a public-facing event and the introduction of the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good, followed by a fireside chat between Matthew Hawn and Robert Cailliau, co-inventor of the World Wide Web.

4.3.5. JUST Industry Data Week Schedule

Monday, 16 September: Inspirational talks

10:00 → 10:15: Michela Magas: Welcome to the JUST Industry Data Week

10:15 → 11:15: Opening keynote: **Frédéric Verhelst**, Head of Data Office at TotalEnergies EP Danmark: Embracing the Future of AI in industry - collaborative efforts and enhanced solutions

11:15 → 12:00: Diana Popa, Delft University of Technology: Data and Technological Sovereignty – Bridging digitalisation and security challenges.

12:00 → 13:00: Lunch and networking

13:00 → 16:30: Knowledge Exchange Sessions

Speakers:

- **AnnMarie Thomas**, founder of Playful Learning Lab
- **Christian Sahlén**, CEO Actia Nordic
- **Dawn Lim**, Executive Director, DesignSingapore Council
- **Fredrik Eriksson**, Knowit Insight Öst
- **Amir Garmabaki**, Luleå Technical University
- **Jon Green for Marianne Kemmer**, Executive Director, Indoor Air Quality Society
- **Amit Patwardhan**, Luleå Technical University
- **Erik Källman**, RISE
- **Ivo Emanuilov**, Senior Researcher IP & ICT Law, Industry Commons Foundation

16:30 → 17:00: Coffee Break and networking

17:00 → 18:00: Sound for Urban Environments Session

Speakers:

- **Niklas Rönnerberg**, Linköping University
- **Duncan Geere**, Loud Numbers
- **Matthew Hawn**, CEO Fictioneers

18:00 → 18:45: Exclusive live interview with **Elisabeth Sjöstrand**, R&D Manager, Ericsson

Tuesday, 17 September: Global Brainstorming

10:00 → 10:10: Welcome and introduction to Global Brainstorming

10:15 → 12:30: Provocations and Global Brainstorming

Speakers and topics:

- **Kat Austen**, JUST Data collection for training AI agents
- **Amit Patwardhan and Naveen Venkatesh**, AI Revolution LTU Data Labs: micro-measurement data for security in mining, railways and construction
- **Diana Popa**, Delft University of Technology – Tug of war: values and security for trustworthy AI

13:30 → 15:00: Provocations and Global Brainstorming

Speakers and topics:

- **Erik Källman**, RISE - Space Data Lab 3.0: the temporal dimension in satellite data
- **Grant Smith**, Soundcamp Cooperative - Acoustic Commons: Sound for urban environments

15:00 → 15:30: Coffee Break and networking

15:30 → 17:00: Provocations and Global Brainstorming

Speakers and topics:

- **Luís Bettencourt**, University of Chicago (live online) – Just uses of data in cities

Figure 14: Ravi Kapur presenting the ARTEO project

Wednesday, 18 September

10:00 → 17:00: Experimentations track

Field trip, cross-domain data collection and prototyping led by Grant Smith and Gawain Hewitt.

13:00 → 13:45: ArtEO: Empowering Artists with Earth Observation Data

ArtEO is a non-profit initiative founded by Imperative Space, dedicated to bridging the gap between artists and satellite Earth observation (EO) data. ArtEO enables artists across all disciplines to explore environmental data, fostering creative works that reflect our planet's changing climate. This session will showcase insights from the initial Pioneer phase, featuring artworks developed with EO data, including contributions from artists present at JUST Data Week.

14:00 → 16:00: Deconstructing AI Literacy Workshop

Workshop led by Diana Popa from Delft University of Technology and the digiNEB project: Deconstructing AI literacy – a role based approach to defining relevant AI literacy. By engaging in conflicting narratives around what is paramount when developing, deploying and using AI systems we will negotiate adaptive AI governance frameworks and AI literacy responsibilities. In this pursuit both digital and analogue technologies are welcome.

14:00 → 15:00: Jan Bang: Building a Better Sounding World (Figure 15 above: Jan Bang)

For over 30 years, Jan Bang has created immersive, evolving sonic landscapes through innovative use of live remixing and collaboration. His presentation and demonstration explores the art and philosophy of live sampling, and provides insights into how electronic manipulation and spontaneous creativity can forge new musical intersections and transform the way we experience sound.

15:00 → 17:00: Sound experimentation, collaborative performance and improvisation in response to experimentation activities. With Jan Bang, Kat Austen, Fredrik Folkestad, Jung In Jung, Andrea Cerrato, Tom de Majo, Anthony Cowie, Kirsi Mustalahti.

Thursday, 19 September

09:30 → 10:00: Welcome Coffee

10:00 → 12:30: Synthetic and Health Data day

Speakers:

- **Jonathan Converse:** Health Data Innovation Platform (HDIP), TRE4HealthAI and the Health regulatory sandbox
- **Frédéric Verhelst,** Head of Data Office, TotalEnergies EP Danmark: Ontologies and knowledge graphs
- **Andreas Hager:** The Health Makerspace: collaborative decision-making and patient-controlled information flows

- **Björn Larsson**, Introducing the Gothenburg health companies
- **Huaqing Li**, CEO Gynius Plus AB: Empowerment of medical workers through health data – from innovation to scale up and impact in East Africa
- **Sara Nozohouri**, Associate Director, Business Process Manager in clinical operation, AstraZeneca: Process aspects of data management and data privacy in clinical studies
- **Ivo Emanuilov**, IP and ICT Law, Industry Commons Foundation: EU Health Data Space in the context of the AI Act, Data Act and Data Governance Act

12:30 → 13:30: Lunch and networking

13:30 → 15:00: Erick Johnson, LiU: Synthetic Data Workshop

Flattening the world – ontological aspects of data, including the synthetic kind

A hands-on data workshop that explores the relationship between ontology and epistemology, and the production of meta-data to bring insights from critical data studies into conversation with synthetic structured data, intersectional hallucinations and their relationship to ML models. You will not need a computer, but you will need a pencil or a pen. Come prepared to work outside your comfort zone.

15:00 → 15:30: Coffee Break and networking

15:30 → 17:00: Synthetic and Health Data day

Speakers:

- **Åsa Skagerhult**, Business Architect & **Tomas Jussing**, Chief Data Officer, RÖ: Using standardised health data as an accelerator to strengthen future healthcare
- **Erik Ylipää**, AI Support Expert, and **Betül Tove Eren**, Data Sharing Lead, AIDA Data Hub: Data and services for innovation in data driven precision health
- **Joel Petterson**, AI in Healthcare, RÖ: Addressing the Complexities of Metadata and Health Data Extraction in Digital Pathology
- **Sten-Erik Björling**, Senior Data Scientist, Industry Commons Foundation: Proposal for pre-flight for health

Friday, 20 September

10:00 → 10:15: Welcome to the JUST Data Day for Social Good and introductions to Linköping Science Park with **Lena Miranda**, CEO Linköping Science Park and **Michela Magas**, NEB High Level Round Table

10:15 → 11:50: AI for Social Good: JUST Living Environments

Speakers:

- **Robert Cailliau**, formerly of CERN, the European Laboratory for Particle Physics, and First WWW Pioneer: Benevolence and invention
- **Kat Austen**, Participatory ethical approaches to the generation of datasets for training AI agents
- **Petter Ericson**, Data Ethics and the AI Policy Lab
- **Michela Magas**, JUST Data Practice – judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent

11:30 → 12:30: JUST Living Environments: Conversation moderated by Franklin van der Hoeven (TU Delft) with Francesca Rizzo (POLIMI), Kirsi Mustalahti (ACCAC), Diana Popa, (TU Delft), Stefan Holmlid (Linköping University)

12:30 → 13:30: Lunch and networking

13:30 → 13:55: **Ivo Emanuilov**, IP and ICT Law, Industry Commons Foundation: AI Act for social good?

14:00 → 14:40: Models for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation.

Launch of the digiNEB Handbook for EU Ecosystemic Regional Innovation and lessons learned from Linköping EU Capital of Innovation.

Figure 16: Conversation moderated by **Andrew Dubber** with **Laura Hagemann Arellano**, Joint Research Centre, European Commission; **Lena Miranda**, CEO Linköping Science Park; **Jan Åman**, The Norrlands Model and Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook, and **Michela Magas**, NEB High Level Round Table.

14:45 → 15:25: Roofs Over Our Heads: JUST Rooftops and Cognitive Cities.

Conversation moderated by **Andrew Dubber**: **Sheela Patel** (NEB HLRT/Roof-Over-Our-Heads), **Tom Minderhoud** (UN Studio), **Nuno Nunes** (Bauhaus of the Seas/ITI Lisbon)

15:30 → 16:00: Coffee Break and networking

16:00 → 18:00: Preview of the JUST Data Week results: Experiments for Social Good

18:00 → 18:15: Inauguration of the Susan Lesley Bland Prize for Social Good

18:15 → 19:00: Fireside chat with **Robert Cailliau** and **Matthew Hawn**: Susan Lesley Bland and stories from the www.

Saturday, 21 September

17:00 → 19:00: JUST Data Exclusives: Public Showcase

Results from the week of experiments with creative data applications presented to the public, including Mikael Sanfridson, Mayor of the City of Linköping and the Chair of the Board of Directors of Linköping Science Park, Mari Hultgren.

Figure 17, AnnMarie Thomas on playful learning based on her experience of working with Lego Education

4.3.6. Inspirational talks

The Monday programme at JUST Industry Data Labs featured the following inspirational keynote presentations that galvanised the diverse community of experts around NEB principles, digital ethics, creative practice and co-creation.

Semantic Knowledge Graphs

Frédéric Verhelst, Head of Data Office at TotalEnergies EP Danmark, discussed the application of semantic knowledge graphs in addressing the energy sector's data challenges. He demonstrated how these tools can bridge data silos, enhance decision-making, and improve compliance. By fostering structured knowledge systems, Frédéric highlighted their potential to support regional innovation and sustainability efforts in an increasingly data-driven world.

Digital Sovereignty

Diana Popa, a researcher at Delft University of Technology, explored digital sovereignty and its significance in balancing technological development with regional resilience. She examined the risks associated with dependency on commercial technology providers and stressed the importance of secure, locally managed digital frameworks. Her talk provided insights into how robust digital sovereignty can underpin sustainable innovation.

Data Sonification

Duncan Geere, an information designer and co-founder of the sonification studio Loud Numbers, presented the transformative potential of data sonification in making complex information accessible. He shared examples, including the sonification of wildfire data, demonstrating how sound can connect people with environmental data in engaging and meaningful ways, fostering awareness and action.

Open Data

Fredrik Eriksson, a consultant at Knowit in Sweden, shared his expertise in creating sustainable open data ecosystems. He discussed the challenges of standardisation and transparency while collaborating with municipalities and national agencies. Fredrik emphasised how open data can empower communities and drive innovation tailored to regional needs.

Playfulness in Collaboration

AnnMarie Thomas, founder of the Playful Learning Lab, a mechanical engineer and educator, reflected on how playfulness can catalyse creativity and problem-solving in interdisciplinary collaborations. Drawing on her work with the Playful Learning Lab, she highlighted how curiosity and experimentation can spark innovative ideas, particularly in complex or technical fields.

Innovation in Tech Development

Christian Sahlén, CEO of Actia Nordic, shared his company’s journey from a small engineering team in Linköping to a global enterprise in the automotive tech industry. He discussed the importance of strategic partnerships and innovative design in scaling operations, showcasing how local expertise and problem-solving can drive sustainable growth.

Figure 18: Presentation by Dawn Lim, Executive Director of the DesignSingapore Council

Redesigning Care

Dawn Lim, Executive Director of the DesignSingapore Council, presented Singapore’s design-led approach to creating inclusive care systems. She explored how innovative policies and community design integrate empathy and accessibility, offering a model for fostering health and well-being in both urban and regional contexts.

Indoor Air Quality

Jon Green, founder of the Indoor Air Quality Society, discussed the importance of addressing invisible environmental challenges. He highlighted ongoing projects linking air quality data with health outcomes, underscoring the need for public awareness and regulation. Jon’s work demonstrates how data can drive systemic improvements in public health.

Sonification and Sound Design

Niklas Rönnerberg, Senior Associate Professor in Sonification and Sound Design at Linköping University, explored how sound can make complex data more intuitive. By using techniques such as parameter mapping and auditory icons, he illustrated how auditory experiences can enhance understanding in areas like environmental monitoring and urban planning.

Figure 19: Presentation by Matthew Hawn about data narratives.

Personal Data Stories and Identity

Matthew Hawn, CEO of Fictioneers, and a pioneering technology and music industry expert, reflected on the evolution of digital identity and data ownership. He shared insights into the importance of individual control over personal data and the role of open-source solutions in fostering equitable digital environments. His talk highlighted the growing need for ethical approaches to managing digital footprints.

Legal Perspectives on Data Ownership

Ivo Emanuilov, IP lawyer and senior researcher at the Industry Commons Foundation examined the legal frameworks surrounding data ownership. He discussed the limitations of existing systems and proposed collaborative, transparent approaches to data governance. Ivo's insights emphasised the importance of balancing innovation with responsible data management.

Intelligent Asset Management

Amit Patwardhan, a PhD candidate at Luleå University of Technology, discussed intelligent asset management strategies, focusing on predictive maintenance and digital twins. He demonstrated how data-driven approaches can optimise efficiency and reduce environmental impact in industries such as mining and railways, showcasing the potential for sustainable industrial transformation.

Space Data Lab

Erik Källman, a researcher at RISE, presented the Space Data Lab initiative, which integrates satellite Earth observation data for diverse applications. He explained how regional access to high-resolution data supports innovation in environmental monitoring, urban planning, and agriculture, illustrating the potential for open data to drive localised solutions.

4.3.7. Global Brainstorming

The **Global Brainstorming day** at JUST Industry Data Week aimed at exploring the ethical, creative, and practical dimensions of data use across diverse fields. Attended in person and accessible globally online, the event brought together experts, innovators, and members of the NEB community from various disciplines to engage in collaborative discussions. The purpose was to critically examine how data can be collected, shared, and applied in ways that are ethical, inclusive, sustainable and future-focused.

The day featured a series of provocations — short, impactful presentations by leading thinkers in AI, data ethics, urban planning, sound studies, industrial applications, and satellite technologies. These sparked dialogue, offering participants unique insights and framing the critical questions that guided subsequent brainstorming sessions. The provocateurs challenged assumptions, shared real-world examples, and posed provocative questions about the potential and pitfalls of data practices.

Participants, both in-person and online, engaged actively in these discussions, while also building on the provocations with their own perspectives, ideas, and questions. A Miro board served as a collaborative space where participants captured key points, proposed solutions, and documented insights. The format encouraged the blending of expert knowledge with diverse participant input, fostering an interdisciplinary exchange of ideas.

Figure 20: A multi-way discussion in response to Diana Popa from TU Delft and her presentation on values and security for trustworthy AI.

Summary of insights:

Discussions underscored the importance of **designing data systems that reflect diverse perspectives and aspirations**, rather than simply mirroring existing inequalities. There was a strong emphasis on transparency, accountability, and environmental responsibility as critical elements of trustworthy AI.

Participants **highlighted the power of alternative data modalities**. Sound was highlighted as a unique and often overlooked data source that can reveal hidden patterns and foster community engagement. The use of open-source tools was encouraged for their ability to democratise access to complex data systems, particularly in fields like satellite data and urban planning.

Across the sessions, participants reflected on the tension between standardised, global approaches to data and **the need for locally tailored, context-sensitive solutions**. The importance of thinking beyond immediate needs and using data to shape sustainable, equitable futures emerged as a central theme.

Provocation 1: Kat Austen – JUST Data Collection for Training AI Agents

Figure 21: Presentation by Kat Austen on training AI agents with collaborative collection of data

Artist and researcher Kat Austen’s session challenged participants to reimagine how data is collected and utilised for training AI systems. She framed AI as an entity being raised by the world, and argued that its training datasets shape the values and biases embedded in its outputs. She also proposed that AI datasets often reflect the biases and limitations of their creators, leading to models that perpetuate existing inequalities. Austen stressed the importance of participatory approaches that involve a diverse range of voices, including non-human and ecological perspectives. The session’s central question was whether AI could be trained not only to reflect the world as it currently exists but to help envision and create more equitable and sustainable futures.

Figure 22: Kat Austen presented one of the most quoted provocations of the Global Brainstorming day: participants continued to refer to this idea in discussions and experiments that followed.

Takeaways:

Inclusivity and Context: Participants noted the importance of foundational questions like “Who generated the data?” and “Who benefits?” A comment on the Miro board asked, “Was there informed consent?” reflecting concerns about ethical considerations in data collection.

Aspirational Futures: Kat’s provocation, “What if we trained AI not on fragments of the shape of the world that is, but on the shapes of the worlds to which we collectively aspire?” resonated strongly. A Miro post-it elaborated: “AI can help us imagine better futures rather than reinforcing existing inequalities.”

Diverse Data Sources: Participants highlighted the need for diversity in data collection to ensure models are representative. One note mentioned, “AI should stand for ‘alien intelligence,’ drawing on many kinds of worlds,” referencing a more imaginative and inclusive approach.

Provocation 1 - Kat Austen

JUST Data collection for training AI agents

Who/what generated the data?

Who or what does the data represent

Are the interests of the data subject represented?

Was there informed consent?

Was the data subject invited to use the data?
Andrew Dubber

Who benefits?

What if we trained AI not on the fragments of the shape of the world that is

What if we trained on the shapes of the world

"When dealing with inherited data, treat it with the same caution as using someone else's toothbrush"
Cassie KOZYRKOV

How do we communicate a datasource is fragmented? How can we flag or annotate it with what's missing?
Matthew Hawn

How can we democratize the process of gathering data globally

How can we help participants in data collection to start using the data themselves? What tools can we offer to people who help us collect the data to find the collective results useful and valuable to them?
Matthew Hawn

"most information doesn't represent truth but connects and organizes ideas and people, acting as a "social nexus."
Yuval Noah Harari

Counter-provocation: What if we already have enough data?

do we need "nutritional content" labeling for data sets so non-data scientistss can understand what we're consuming ?
Matthew Hawn

What data is needed to train AI to make a better future? Do we have that data? Who chooses what is 'better'?

AI should stand for "alien intelligence". AI could become "new kinds of gods."
Yuval Noah Harari

AI is not intelligent, but intelligence is also not a useful term
 1

how to prevent ai training on ai perpetuating bias

how can we better communicate the value of participatory data collection to marginal groups? What are the levers to support inclusion that build value for participants?
Matthew Hawn

Who is affected by the outcome?
Kat

How can we build in best practice from participation into datasets for AI? - bespoke AI trained on crowdsourced data for specific problems

AI data sets can be conceived of in the same way as governance - it takes time and effort to be involved in stewarding them - how do we shape society to make space for this in people's lives?
Kat

As we fine-tune AI models, can we build in data fragility/bias into the vectors or tagging that we're building to query/process it?
Matthew Hawn

Kat Austen - # Sound # Video #Performance # Sculpture
 Kat Austen is a person. In her artistic practice, she focuses on environmental issues. She melds disciplines and media, creating sculptural and new media installations, performances and participatory work. Austen's practice is underpinned by extensive ...

Nutrition Facts

Amount Per Serving	
Calories 60	
% Daily Value*	
Total Fat	12g
Sodium	2g
Total Carbohydrate	1g
Dietary Fiber	1g
Sugars	1g
Protein	1g
*Percent Daily Values are based on a diet of other people's secrets.	

Provocation 2: Amit Patwardhan and Naveen Venkatesh – AI Revolution in Mining, Railways, and Construction

Figure 23: Presentation by Amit Patwardhan, Luleå University of Technology.

This session explored the transformative potential of AI in industrial settings, with a specific focus on mining, railways, and construction. Data scientists and industry experts Amit Patwardhan and Naveen Venkatesh highlighted how point cloud data and digital twins are being used to predict failures, optimise maintenance schedules, and improve safety standards. They emphasised the practical benefits of integrating AI into industrial processes, while also discussing the challenges of scaling these technologies in environments with limited digital infrastructure or expertise. They highlighted the importance of collaboration with other domains, such as service and sound design, in terms of integrating safe and sustainable data systems.

Takeaways:

Risk Detection: One participant reflected on the railway project: “Sweden has 10,000 km of cabling; automation is key. Point cloud data helps identify risks like cable sagging that could cause costly failures.”

Domain Expertise: A Miro note captured the importance of preserving industry knowledge: “How do we capture the wisdom of engineers with 50+ years of experience and integrate it into digital systems?”

Sound as a Tool: Patwardhan highlighted the knowledge acquired on the previous day from a presentation about data sonification research, and elaborated a novel concept of using sound to identify structural issues through sonification. A contributor’s note read, “Sound is connected to our lizard brain—quicker to detect anomalies than visual data.”

Augmented Reality: The HoloLens example showed how field operators could visualise point cloud data in real time. This led to comments like, “Augmented reality can make industrial data actionable and accessible on-site.” Once again, collaboration with experts from other domains, such as design and creative applications was highlighted.

Provocation 2 - Amit Patwardhan and Naveen Venkatesh

AI Revolution, LTU Data Labs: micro-measurement data for security in mining, railways and construction

Where does the responsibility lie if something goes wrong when people are using tools for engineering that rely on AI?	The most important thing to come out of a mine is the miner.	How do you gauge the readiness for an industry partner to begin the digital transformation process? Getting ready to transform your company requires some organisation and governance change. What are the signs that they are ready for this change? How do you help them to get there? Matthew Hawn	Does this methodology require industry to completely transform how they collect data or does this build on existing data collection points? Matthew Hawn	How could you make your AI Factory and digital twins methodology more "human" and work with existing processes & the tech stack for the people or computers you want to work with. As presented, it feels Early monolithic and not open to collaboration and evolution. Matthew Hawn	Visitor
worth reading: John McPhee's Book "Encounters with the Archdruid" It is split into three parts, each covering environmental, geological, & controversial issues with his ideological enemies. The book chronicles his struggles against miners, developers and finally the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration . The dialog between them is fascinating and what's learned on both sides is transformative. Matthew Hawn	hearing evolved first - then our eyes to confirm. Matthew Whiteside	How might you add the "non-human" voices to your data collection methodology (as Kat's provocation suggests we need to do to make it JUST.) Matthew Hawn	Sound is connected to our lizard brain		

Provocation 3: Diana Popa – Values and Security for Trustworthy AI

Figure 24: Presentation by Diana Popa, TU Delft.

Diana Popa, Researcher at Delft University of Technology and digiNEB colleague presented an exploration of the values underpinning trustworthy AI, calling attention to the challenges of ensuring fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI systems. She highlighted the inherent tensions between rapid innovation and ethical considerations, particularly in the face of increasing environmental and social impacts. Diana urged participants to consider not just the technical attributes of AI systems, but the broader societal and environmental consequences of their deployment.

Takeaways:

Trustworthiness and Ethics: On the Miro board, participants defined trustworthy AI as “accountable, unbiased, reliable, representative.” Another post-it stated, “Transparency and environmental accountability must be part of trustworthiness.”

Environmental Impact: A note pointed to a Guardian article shared during the session: “AI models have 7-8x the environmental footprint previously reported—this must be addressed.”

Unintended Consequences: Referring to Marshall McLuhan’s theories, one participant noted, “What looks like the benefit of AI may become its harm. For example, social media began as a connector and became a divider.”

Due Diligence: Participants acknowledged the challenges of assessing AI applications: “Criteria for due diligence on AI are still underdeveloped—what’s ethical today may not be tomorrow.”

Tug of war: Values and security for trustworthy AI

Trustworthy AI means...

Based on which criteria do you choose an AI Application?

The environmental impact of AI: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2024/sep/12/data-center-gas-emissions-tech>

<https://bfj.uchicago.edu/insights/the-adoption-of-chatgpt/>

Trust requires a negotiation... <https://www.oxfordjournals.org/doi/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190264187.013.10>

We need to distinguish between AI that extends or empowers us vs AI that leverages our data against us or against marginalized groups. <https://www.oxfordjournals.org/doi/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190264187.013.10>

What are the positives? What about people who struggle with writing, for instance?

Artist and Technologist John Maeda on <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8K5W> (2024 SXSW talk)

The responsibility of the artist/designer to engage with AI

Due diligence on social media selection

Responsible design of tools

Controlling information flows means controlling people's agency and decisions - AI is being shaped as a source of information, the basis for which is poorly understood and controlled by the few.

Andrew's McLuhan: - what does it enhance? - what does it replace? - What does it retrieve?

"We have no moral" - a google AI engineer's point that building a AI monopoly may not be possible

By 2026, AI models from organizations that operationalize AI transparency, trust and security will achieve a 50% improvement in terms of adoption, business goals and user acceptance. Source: Gartner

Risk aversion and risk-taking: Where are the areas each are important?

Consider what 'business models' are actually not viable unless you externalise a lot of the cost

We are miles apart compare the [Open AI charter](#) vs the [Principles for Secure, Scalable, Safe AI](#).

Create AI safeguarding principles like we have created [AI4People](#) principles

Start with principles before you move to tools. This is from [https://www.oxfordjournals.org/doi/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190264187.013.10](#)

What is "the AI"?

A gathering of highly educated people will speak about the Big Bad

There are probably only 5 teachers qualified to talk about AI in Sweden

how does cultural or racial code-switching make it hard to collect data on intersectional or under-represented groups?

What does trustworthy AI mean to you? 17 responses

extension of me, reliable, unbiased, accountable, transparent, accurate, lawful, representative, reproducible, explainable, fair, aligned, benevolent, trusted data sources, utopia

Based on which criteria do you choose a certain AI application? 13 responses

The price	Availability	accountability and auditability and explainability	Ease of use, quality of results, fairness
Contractual warranties	can it get me away from the 'blank slate' inertia when writing something to get ideas	Amplifies my human abilities	Fit to the current problem
Repairable			AI for ai Vs AI for the problem
if there is a free version to try	explainability, business model, and a two-way path to getting my data	I already pay for ChatGPT for a list of processes, and don't	

Provocation 4: Erik Källman – Space Data Lab 3.0

Figure 25: Presentation by Erik Källman, Space Data Lab 3.0, Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE).

Joining the session remotely, Erik Källman, Researcher at RISE (Research Institutes of Sweden), discussed the untapped potential of satellite data for addressing critical global challenges, such as climate change and disaster management. He focused on the temporal dimension of this data, emphasising its ability to provide dynamic, time-based insights into long-term processes. Erik underscored the importance of open-source tools and system redundancy in making satellite data more accessible and reliable, noting that these are crucial for ensuring equitable participation in space-based research.

Takeaways:

System Redundancy: A note summarised: “Heterogeneity of hardware is essential. Fault tolerance and redundancy are crucial for satellite data systems.”

Access and Expertise: The scarcity of expertise in handling satellite data was a key point. A Miro post-it read, “How do we build capacity for processing complex spatial datasets? Expertise is limited.”

Open-Source Collaboration: Participants were enthusiastic about the role of open-source tools. One comment read, “Open-source enables shared value—collaboration reduces the barriers to innovation.”

Temporal Analysis: Erik’s emphasis on analysing changes over time was seen as transformative. A note observed, “Temporal satellite data gives insights into climate change and urban growth in ways static data cannot.”

Provocation 4 - Erik Källman

Space Data Lab 3.0: The temporal dimension in satellite data

System redundancy is essential	Heterogeneity of hardware and fault-tolerance reminds me a bit of Erlang	Traditionally, a big problem with moving from simple test calcs to HPC was parallelization, are GIS doing enough vector processing etc. in R?	love the composability of this approach and the awareness of existing tech stacks for partners.	Love the opensource elements that help you evolve this stack while contributing to the shared value.
Scarcity of expertise and limited access to data			Matthew Hawn	Matthew Hawn
			<p>Is this a vertical application stack (ie only useable for SpaceED data) or is it something that could be re-used for other kinds of public AI data tools?</p> <p>ie: is this environment something that can be reproduced for other public AI data projects? Is this a model for groups like the Foundation for Public Code to follow?</p>	
			Matthew Hawn	

Provocation 5: Grant Smith – Acoustic Commons: Sound for Urban Environments

Figure 23: Presentation by Grant Smith, Soundcamp.

Sound artist and member of Soundcamp cooperative, Grant Smith’s session explored the innovative use of sound as data, focusing on how soundscapes can provide unique insights into urban environments. He introduced ecoacoustics as a method for monitoring ecological and social dynamics, arguing that sound offers a powerful alternative lens through which to understand urban challenges. The discussion also touched on how sound could be used for activism and community building, with Grant suggesting a “Slow Data” movement to mirror the intentionality of Slow Food.

Takeaways:

Sound as a Lens: A Miro note encapsulated the central idea: “Soundscapes reveal invisible dynamics—ecological health, community activity, even urban injustice.”

Community Transmission: Participants discussed how sound could foster collective awareness. A note suggested, “OpenStreetMaps for sound—communities can document their local soundscapes to fill gaps where data is missing.”

Slow Data Movement: Grant proposed a "Slow Data" movement inspired by Slow Food, emphasising intentional and ethical data collection. One participant added, “Slow data values quality over quantity—important for building trust and meaning.”

Acoustic Activism: A note observed, “Ecoacoustics can replace bioacoustics—sound can inspire environmental action in ways visual data cannot.”

Provocation 5 - Grant Smith

Acoustic Commons: Sound for urban environments

Idiot in a Smart City

The sound of sounds is an obstacle to getting to the data

Ecoacoustics as an approach to replace bioacoustics

book recommendation: *The Foghorn's Lament* by Jennifer Lucy Allen
Matthew Haan

ecological activist radio

Soundcamp Cooperative
Soundcamp link tree

Communities of transmission

It would have been horrifying and illustrating to have collected soundscapes across Gaza over the last year

what does an ecoacoustic data collection toolkit look like?
We all carry headphones but why don't more of us carry microphones?
How might we encourage others to do this kind of data collection and field work?
Matthew Haan

andrew bird's *Exile/ations River*
"The ambient sounds of the eastemay combine with bird's playing and use of sonic effects to create a heightened sense of tranquility"
Bandcamp link
Matthew Haan

"The world is a recording studio where people, places, and things become the instruments." - Stuart H
Stuart Hyatt's Field Works
Bandcamp links to listen
Matthew Haan

"Open Street Maps allow people to draw themselves in where Google doesn't ascribe value."
- Michela introducing Grant

widen our community of practice, community of transmission.
not building an audience; building a community together

the interference archive
like tom deMajo asked, I want to hear more about this and understand it more
Matthew Haan

Should we have a "Slow Data" movement like we have "Slow Food" movement?
similar maybe to the Long Now Foundation?
Matthew Haan

"not field recorders, we are documenting something."
"making radio with others" to create collective leverage

The value of the data and the value of the metadata are not necessarily connected or similar

collect the data but also collect the rationale, the metadata and circumstances under which the data was collected.

mark peter wright - *Listening After Nature*
LISTENING AFTER NATURE
Matthew Haan

observation effect

data as toothbrush. If you're going to use someone else's, you want to know whom (and where/how)
Cassie Kozyrov

spectacle or specimen

the audience is listening

coastline paradox. The more granular the measure, the longer the distance

Provocation 6: Luís Bettencourt – Just Uses of Data in Cities

Figure 26: Presentation by Luís Bettencourt, University of Chicago.

Professor of Ecology and Evolution in the Sociology department at the University of Chicago, Luís Bettencourt addressed the ethical and practical challenges of using data for urban planning and governance. He emphasised that urbanisation is as much about shifts in behaviour and knowledge as it is about physical infrastructure. He argued for equitable data practices that prioritise local knowledge and community participation, while also warning about the potential pitfalls of poorly managed urban data systems.

Figure 27: An shown example of how urban data shapes the future of cities.

Takeaways:

Urbanisation as Development: A note summarised: “Urbanisation is about behaviour change—data can shape how cities grow and how people interact with their environments.”

City Planning Failures: Participants reflected on the dual potential of urban data. One comment read, “City planning has improved lives but also led to great failures—how do we avoid repeating these?”

Equity and Privacy: Discussions emphasised the need for ethical frameworks. A Miro post-it noted, “We must respect privacy and local knowledge in urban data collection.”

Future-Oriented Data: Luís’s framing of data as inherently future-oriented struck a chord. A participant wrote, “Data shapes the future of cities—it must be used to reflect aspirations, not just current needs.”

Provocation 6 - Luis Bettencourt

Home | Luis Bettencourt
Current Positions: Service, Urban Science and Practice. Much of my research and service are presently dedicated to the scientific study of cities and associated practices to help make our societies more just and sustainable. The guiding vision is to approach...

Just uses of data in cities

bettenccourt@chicago.edu

Connection through Sheela Patel - Roof Over Our Heads

Book: Luis Bettencourt *Introduction to Urban Science*

[Chicago Data Portal](#)

urbanization = development

people's knowledge and behaviour change

City planning is very much a thing, and has been used to great effect in improving lives, and lead to many failures

Book: Hans Rosling *Factfulness*

Is planning bad just because it is not infallible?

Harkive (2013-2022) <https://harkive.org/>

Which Humans? by Atari et al <https://psyarxiv.com/5b26t/>

data is always future oriented.

It is the theory that determines what can be observed

The problems of using only quantitative data instead of adding qualitative data

qual data = what happened
quant data = why it happened

Matthew Hawn

examples of the inadequacies of data include things like [urbanism](#)

We need to get better at asking the right questions of our data when we're using it. And building the right tools.

It is the theory that determines what can be observed

Book: James C Scott *Seeing Like a State*

saul alinsky-activists using data to create political capital for change - [wikipedia](#)

Book: Catherine D'Ignazio and Lauren F Klein *Data Feminism*

tom: do we support current paradigms of power by using hegemonic data sets? How can we get change that?

Luís: the answer is more data sets from the less powerful to help combine others to drive change.

Petter: it's important not to let data obscure power

Book: Brian Merchant *Blood in the Machine*

Te Hiku Media (Te Reo Maori dialect preservation and data sovereignty)

Book: Pet Rabies Vaccine Requirements as a Cautionary Control Grid Tale

Home: sobat.com

Solari Report - Actionable Intelligence to Live a Free & Inspired Life

Nothing on the Solari Report should be taken as individual investment advice. Anyone seeking investment advice for his or her personal financial situation is advised to seek out a qualified advisor or advisors and provide as much information as possible...

Cory Doctorow's speech to defcon 2024 *"Automation or die"*

petter in the Zoom comments: "There are non-luddites and they have a lot of good points, just like the original luddites, lol"

Brian Merchant - [Blood in the Machine](#) book and newsletter

Web3 is going awol.

ETHICS Molly White

an example of using data to shine a line on malevolence in big tech

4.3.8. digiNEB Day: JUST Living Environments Panel

Figure 28: JUST Living Environments panel during the digiNEB day devoted to AI for Social Good.

The **JUST Living Environments** Panel, moderated by digiNEB Coordinator, Frank van der Hoeven from TU Delft, focused on inclusion, participatory design, and the ethical integration of technology in urban and social spaces. Frank opened the session by framing the discussion around the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles: beauty, sustainability, and inclusion, and shared an example from Rotterdam, highlighting the stark health disparities between neighbourhoods and the need for innovative approaches to tackle these systemic issues.

digiNEB EAB member, **Kirsi Mustalahti** of ACCAC introduced the concept of ‘radical inclusion’, emphasising the importance of involving everyone from the design phase to ensure that communities’ needs are truly understood and addressed. She highlighted the need for tools and environments that foster creativity and participation for individuals with diverse backgrounds and abilities.

digiNEB team member and researcher at TU Delft **Diana Popa** discussed governance in the context of AI and how combining human and AI decision-making can yield better outcomes. She addressed the importance of AI literacy, ensuring that communities understand the risks and limitations of the technology while leveraging its potential.

Stefan Holmlid, Professor of Service Design at Linköping University and member of the Swedish NEB community, emphasised the interconnectedness of services in living environments and the importance of addressing the relationships between communities and their surroundings, rather than focusing solely on isolated interventions. He highlighted the double-edged nature of inclusion efforts, which can unintentionally create exclusion if not carefully managed.

Francesca Rizzo, digiNEB EAB member and Professor of Design from Politecnico di Milano called attention to the systemic issues often created by urban regeneration projects, such as gentrification, which can displace existing communities despite intentions of inclusion. She stressed the importance of co-

production in participatory design, moving beyond listening to communities to empowering them to design solutions themselves.

The panel discussed inclusion and exclusion, noting that while inclusion is a goal, mechanisms of exclusion often persist, especially for marginalised groups lacking access to resources or networks. The panel examined how AI could be integrated into urban design while addressing its current limitations, particularly in understanding human complexity and emotions. There was a strong focus on viewing living environments as interconnected systems, where interventions in one area have ripple effects elsewhere. Participants discussed how beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity could be realised through community engagement and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Takeaways: The panel concluded with a **call for greater attention to the relationships and intersections between communities, systems, and technologies**. It highlighted the importance of **designing not just for communities but with them, while remaining mindful of the unintended consequences of well-meaning interventions**.

4.3.9. DigiNEB Day: Models for Ecosystemic Regional Innovation Panel

Figure 29: Regional innovation panel during the digiNEB day devoted to AI for Social Good.

The JUST Regional Innovation Panel brought together **Jan Åman**, curator and author of the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook; **Michela Magas**, digiNEB partner ICF and NEB HLRT; **Lena Miranda**, CEO of Linköping Science Park and representative of the European Capital of Innovation; and **Laura Hagemann Arellano**, from the European Commission's Joint Research Centre. Moderated by Andrew Dubber (ICF), the session invited NEB projects, Lighthouses and other initiatives to contribute their best practices, co-creation frameworks and case studies to integrate in the book for local and regional policymakers and administrators. The discussion explored models for ecosystemic regional innovation, focusing on how small and local initiatives can address global challenges through scalable, interconnected practices.

Jan Åman opened the discussion by outlining the origins of the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook (see section 5.4 below), which draws heavily on his work in Duved, a small village in northern Sweden. In Duved, Åman implemented a grassroots, community-driven approach to innovation, tackling challenges

like local food systems, sustainable mobility, and housing prototypes. He described Duved as a **"campus without a university,"** where experimental projects were piloted in collaboration with local residents, researchers, and architects. This work highlighted the potential for small, clearly defined communities to serve as testbeds for scalable solutions, with lessons applicable to larger urban areas and global contexts. Åman stressed that innovation often thrives in smaller settings where connections between individuals, businesses, and institutions are stronger, but **success requires creating structured systems for engagement and collaboration.**

Magas reflected on the scalability of these models, connecting them to her work with the New European Bauhaus and the development of the 100 Labs for 100 Regions initiative. She explained how **small, grassroots projects can act as "sparks" for larger systemic change when linked to regional and European-level funding mechanisms.** Magas illustrated this with a funding model she co-developed, where early-stage projects are supported through local and regional funding before scaling up to larger programmes like those facilitated by the European Innovation Council. She noted that this layered approach bridges the funding gaps that often stifle innovation in its early stages, ensuring promising projects can grow and have broader impact.

Laura Hagemann Arellano provided an update on the 100 Labs for 100 Regions initiative. She outlined two key actions: the creation of a **NEB Innovative Funding Advisory Hub**, which connects projects with public and private funding opportunities, and the organisation of **prizes for grassroots initiatives led by small municipalities.** These efforts aim to address the common barriers small projects face, such as limited administrative capacity and access to knowledge while fostering innovation at the community level. Hagemann stressed the importance of supporting municipalities with fewer than 20,000 inhabitants, as these often have the strongest grassroots innovation potential but the least access to funding.

Lena Miranda shared insights from Linköping's journey to becoming a European Capital of Innovation. She described the process of mapping and highlighting innovation within the municipality, including non-technological solutions and new ways of organising services. Miranda emphasised **the importance of combining social innovation with digital tools**, noting that Linköping's smaller size enabled strong networks and collaboration across local government, academia, and industry. She likened smaller cities to "scale-ups," positioned between the agility of villages and the complexity of larger cities, making them ideal environments for testing and refining innovative practices. Examples included city districts designed to be car-free and infrastructure projects prioritising circular models and climate resilience.

A recurring theme throughout the panel was the interplay between local and global scales of innovation. Andrew Dubber asked how small-scale projects can address global challenges such as climate change and public health. Magas and Åman emphasised that **local innovations must be interconnected and contextually adapted to achieve global relevance.** Magas noted that the Regional Innovation Model Handbook aims to collate, document and disseminate these practices, enabling European municipalities to implement and scale similar initiatives.

Åman concluded by highlighting the importance of structural support for local democracy and innovation, noting that traditional funding systems often fail to provide the resources needed to build participatory frameworks. **He called for systemic leadership at the European level to support these transitions, arguing that empowering local actors with tools and resources would lead to more effective and sustainable outcomes.**

Takeaways: The session reinforced the value of ecosystemic regional innovation as a means of addressing complex global issues, by **connecting regional stakeholders**, and **combining social innovation and digital**

tools. It underscored the importance of **linking local efforts to broader networks and funding structures**, while recognising the unique strengths of smaller communities in **fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange for innovative results.**

4.3.10. DigiNEB Day – Roofs Over Our Heads and Cognitive Cities Panel

Figure 30: Panel on cognitive cities during the digiNEB day devoted to AI for Social Good.

The **Roofs Over Our Heads and Cognitive Cities** panel brought together **Sheela Patel** (Founder of SPARC: Society for the Promotion of Area Resource Centres and New European Bauhaus High-Level Roundtable member), **Nuno Nunes** (Professor at ITI Lisbon and coordinator of the Bauhaus of the Seas project), and **Tom Minderhoud** (Architect at UN Studio). Moderated by ICF Senior Researcher Andrew Dubber, the session explored the challenges of informal housing, and the role of digital technologies in creating equitable urban living environments.

Nuno Nunes framed rooftops as an "unconventional design space" with untapped potential for addressing urban challenges. Drawing on lessons from his **Bauhaus of the Seas** project, which focuses on coastal areas, he argued that rooftops could play a similar role in fostering resilience and innovation.

Nunes highlighted **rooftops as spaces for climate adaptation**, suggesting their use for urban cooling through greenery, water collection, and energy generation. He called for recognising rooftops as communal spaces rather than merely architectural limits, stating, "We don't know how to govern our rooftops; we don't consider them as public spaces."

Tom Minderhoud echoed the potential of rooftops, particularly in high-density cities. He described how activating rooftops could create additional layers of usable urban space. However, he noted that achieving this in formal architectural practice requires careful planning and collaboration with policymakers, investors, and communities.

Sheela Patel focused on the realities of informal settlements, where 60% of the population in the Global South lives without formal housing. She shared insights from her **Roof Over Our Heads** project, which works with women's collectives to develop affordable, resilient roofing solutions for self-built homes.

Patel described the challenges faced by informal communities, including extreme weather and exclusion from formal governance. She highlighted the ingenuity of these communities, noting that “98% of these 2 billion people design, construct, and finance their own homes,” often using scavenged materials.

Patel championed **informality as a valuable source of innovation**, stating, “We need to celebrate how people survive in these processes,” while challenging formal architectural education for neglecting this knowledge. She emphasised the **potential for digital tools to empower communities**, mentioning her work on a digital platform to share knowledge about construction materials, safety standards, and designs. However, she cautioned against top-down approaches: “Digital platforms must answer the questions that matter to these communities.”

The panellists examined the role of digital technologies in advancing equitable urban development. Patel described her ambition to use digital tools to empower informal communities through knowledge-sharing platforms, with a focus on the needs of women in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

Tom Minderhoud addressed the implications of digital technologies in formal architectural practice. He explained how his firm uses AI to improve internal knowledge-sharing and inform architectural decisions. However, he warned of risks in deferring too much to technology, particularly regarding intellectual property and the interpretation of data. Minderhoud elaborated on the concept of “**cognitive cities,**” **which integrate machine intelligence to adapt dynamically to urban conditions.** Both Minderhoud and Patel highlighted the importance of **contextualising technology.** Patel emphasised localised solutions and cultural relevance, while Minderhoud advocated for combining human judgement with machine learning to create hybrid approaches.

Nuno Nunes tied the discussion by arguing for a collaborative approach between the Global North and South. He said, “We need to move away from top-down solutions and focus on co-designing locally tailored solutions.”

Patel’s critique of formal urban planning was a central theme of the discussion. She argued that archaic, Eurocentric planning models fail to address the realities of informal settlements, where most urban growth is occurring. She called for a rethinking of planning instruments to accommodate informal construction, stating, “Informality happens because we have very stupid, archaic, pre-colonial planning instruments.” She stressed the need to **bridge the divide between formal and informal housing, both in policy and architectural education.**

Nunes supported this perspective, positioning the Bauhaus of the Seas as an opportunity to learn from informal communities. Minderhoud, while recognising the challenges of reconciling formality and informality, pointed out the complexities of integrating these approaches in formal architectural processes. **He emphasised the role of architects as facilitators, working with policymakers and communities to create inclusive solutions.**

Takeaways: The panel noted the importance of **integrating machine intelligence to adapt dynamically to urban conditions,** but insisted that **technology had to be contextualised within social conditions, bridging the divide between formal and informal housing, both in policy and architectural education.**

4.3.11. Public showcase: engagement of the regional government and the public

Figure 31: Urban data-driven performance by Kat Austing during the public showcase.

The week culminated on Saturday afternoon with a preview of data-driven applications, prototypes and findings from the week of debate and experimentation. ‘The Future Sound of Linköping’, created in collaboration with EDIH and industry partners, included installations, performances, demonstrations, simulations and experiences that were presented to the representatives from the regional government and the public..

Figure 32: Public engagement during showcase day.

4.3.12. Participants and adopters

The strategy for onboarding early adopters to the digiNEB ecosystem during the JUST Industry Data Week included engaging with inspirational talks, contributing to the global brainstorming sessions, participating in data literacy workshops, co-creating digital prototypes in interdisciplinary teams and engaging in discussions about the social impacts of data and AI.

The event attracted a diverse group of professionals, students, and researchers, both in person and online. In total, 128 people registered and participated. They included:

- Researchers, academics, and postdoctoral fellows from institutions such as Linköping University, Karolinska Institute, and TU Delft.
- Professionals in innovation, design, and architecture, such as enterprise architects, business architects, and interaction designers.
- Experts in sustainability and digital technologies, including AI coordinators, environmental artists, and sound designers.
- Practitioners from cultural and creative sectors, including musicians, composers, and photographers.
- Policy officers and organisational leaders representing government bodies, EU initiatives, and private enterprises.
- Students and early-career professionals actively engaged in interdisciplinary projects.

The registered participants represented a wide range of disciplines, contributing expertise in AI, data science, and digital twins, circular value chains, climate adaptation, and environmental design, and came from a broad spectrum of organisations, including:

- Academic and Research Institutions, including universities such as Linköping University, Stockholm University, and TU Delft and specialist institutes like the Nordic Institute of Theoretical Physics and SciLifeLab.
- Large companies, including Ericsson, AstraZeneca, and TotalEnergies Danmark, as well as smaller enterprises such as Actigate, IPScreener, and Fictioneers.
- Public Sector and Non-Profits, including government and regional organisations, such as Region Östergötland and the Ministry of Climate of Estonia, and cultural and creative institutions like the UNESCO Creative Cities Network.
- Creative and Cultural Practitioners such as independent artists, sound designers, and musicians working on innovative projects like urban soundscapes and sonic branding.

4.3.13. Participants' feedback

The following is a selection of voluntary feedback received in writing (sources available):

- *“A week of fantastic and informative, inspirational talks, with many provocations for new modes of thinking about the ways in which data informs both the mundane and creative spheres of our lives. An enriching week – huge thanks!” – Anthony Cowie, PhD Candidate: Science Communication through Sound and Music, composer and sound artist*
- *“Loved the breakout sessions on AI Literacy and the conversations /global brainstorming” – Sean Bradford, Founder and CEO, ORIGIN STØRIES & Emerging Tech Initiatives*

- *“Interesting and robust talk by Robert Cailliau! Thought-provoking series of talks on Friday - particularly the round-table about ecosystemic regional innovation. Some interesting insights from Jan Åman and a particularly inspiring summary about scalability from Lena and Michela.” – Glynn Skerratt, Freelance Sustainability Consultant*
- *“Great admiration of the organizers who continue to invite a wide range of thinkers, educators, practitioners of different disciplines finding ways to build a better world for tomorrow.” – Jan Bang, Composer, Musician, Festival Director*
- *“Awesome event, many many new insights, and great supportive atmosphere. I would have loved it if we had more time for discussions and questions, especially after presentations/panels. I will keep my eye on the future data labs, as I would like to keep my connection to the network and future learning opportunities.” – Ana Kuštrak Korper, Postdoctoral Researcher in Service Design, Linköping University*
- *“I’ve always believed the soul of creativity is lateral thinking. To be able to find the connections between disparate ideas and concepts and turn them into bridges with art and science is magic. This was a week of that sort of magic.” – Matthew Hawn, CEO Fictioneers*
- *“I thought the ArtEO demonstration was very interesting, as was Kat Austen’s presentations. Of course the discussions during Tuesday were also a highlight.” – Petter Ericson, Postdoctoral Researcher and Lecturer, AI Policy Lab, Umeå University*
- *“It extended my network by taking me to Linköping and connect with this world leading innovation campus, but also, I’d the chance to cooperate and interact with very interesting and specialized professionals from Arts and technology world, some of which I expect to continue debating on this themes.” – Mónica Pedro, Data Science Project Manager*
- *“Not only I’ve met brilliant people from different areas of expertise who made me think about how I see my work and how can I improve it, I’ve made possible future work connections.” – Francisca Siza, Documentary filmmaker*

4.3.14. KPIs

As per the impacts listed under Section 4.3 all of our goals for onboarding Early Adopters outlined in Section 4.3.3 have been met or exceeded:

- **KPI 1:** Successful bringing together of digiNEB and EDIH/industry in dedicated workshops resulted from the urgent theme of responsible data use that provided a **shared area of interest:** (i) shared keynote and inspirational sessions; (ii) global brainstorming around common topics, (iii) the Data Literacy workshop, and (iv) discussions initiated by the digiNEB sessions relevant for industrial domains, focusing on data ethics and AI for social good.
- **KPI 2:** **At least three ongoing collaborations** emerged from the bringing together of digiNEB and industry: (i) research and industry projects in the domain of the industrial metaverse combining creative and industrial sectors, (ii) research and industry projects on use case testing of ethical management of data for use in industrial applications in living environments, and (iii) using NEB methods for testing of real-world applications, to meet the needs of EDIH and industry.
- **KPI 3:** The JUST Data event resulted in the onboarding of **68 new Early Adopters** who actively contributed to the joint agenda.

November 7, 2024, Brussels

Europe's wood sector as a driver for the green and digital transition of the built environment

Wood Policy and Innovation Conference

4.4. Wood4Bauhaus event: Onboarding Wood Industry Stakeholders

At the [Wood Policy and Innovation Conference](#) co-hosted by the Wood4Bauhaus Alliance, Bioregions, woodPoP, and Wood Cluster Styria on 7 November 2024 in Brussels, InnovaWood has been the lead coordinator and emphasised in-person engagement to onboard key community leaders and expand the NEB community. This high-profile event highlighted the critical role of the wood sector and industry in driving future competitiveness in housing and addressing the climate crisis. It showcased innovations in wood-based building design and explored how the public sector can champion bio-based construction to combat climate change.

With over 180 participants attending in person, including Members of the European Parliament, EC staff, policymakers, advocacy organisations and industrial leaders, the event provided a unique platform for onboarding a new target group to the NEB movement. Full programme available [here](#).

Why a European Policy Focus on Wood?

The European wood sector is a powerhouse of sustainable innovation, contributing 17.5 million jobs, €1,114 billion in turnover, and 7% of the EU's GDP (FHP 2023). European companies lead globally in sustainable construction, offering versatile solutions for all building types and providing affordable housing and social benefits in both rural and urban areas. To fully unlock this potential, a coordinated European policy approach is essential.

The Role of Wood in Climate and Urban Transformation

Aligned with the New European Bauhaus principles, wood construction combines aesthetic architectural design, sustainable materials, and inclusive urban renewal. Wood products play a pivotal role in decarbonising the built environment by storing carbon in durable materials like structural elements, furniture, and flooring. By scaling up wood construction, cities can transform into large-scale carbon sinks, turning the construction chain into a carbon pump that extracts greenhouse gases from the atmosphere.

The conference underscored the wood sector's strategic importance for Europe's Clean Industrial Deal, offering practical, scalable solutions to achieve climate neutrality while fostering innovation and economic growth. **This in-person event successfully strengthened the NEB community and deepened engagement with policymakers and stakeholders committed to a sustainable future.**

Figure 33: Delegates during the Wood Policy and Innovation Conference.

Part I: EU policy perspective | Setting the scene: A competitive European wood sector addressing the future challenges

The conference began with a presentation focused on the European wood sector's role in addressing future challenges. Moderators Uwe Kies, Secretary General of InnoWood and Chair of Wood4Bauhaus, and Andreja Kutnar, Director of InnoRenew CoE and Professor at the University of Primorska, guided the session. They discussed the sector's capacity to contribute to sustainability, innovation, and competitiveness while responding to evolving societal and environmental needs. This presentation provided a contextual framework for the discussions that followed. The full presentation is available [here](#).

During the opening presentation, Uwe Kies and Andreja Kutnar introduced the New European Bauhaus (NEB) as a central framework guiding innovation and sustainability within the built environment. They outlined how the NEB integrates principles of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity, aligning closely with the values that are followed by the European wood industry. By highlighting examples of NEB-inspired initiatives, they demonstrated how the movement supports the development of sustainable construction practices, fosters collaboration across sectors, and encourages innovative approaches to design and building. This introduction set the tone for the conference, underscoring the importance of aligning the wood sector's future with broader European goals.

New European Bauhaus A call for bio-materials and nature-based solutions

*“We know that the construction sector can even be turned from a carbon source into a sink, if **organic building materials** like wood and smart technologies like AI are applied.”*

Ursula von der Leyen
President of the European Commission
State of the Union Address, Brussels, 16 September 2020

“Reforesting the planet, retrimbering the cities: timber construction is a true silver bullet for climate change.”

Prof. John Schellnhuber
Director Emeritus of the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
Director General of International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)
Wood4Bauhaus Conference, 8 April 2021

Figure 34: The importance of the wood sector and timber construction was highlighted in the opening of the conference in reference to the New European Bauhaus policy.

Part II: Policies and Instrument

In this session, Andreja Kutnar presented on Green Public Procurement and Skills Development: The Case of Slovenia. She explored how Slovenia is incorporating sustainable practices into public procurement, focusing on the role of green criteria in promoting environmentally responsible solutions. She also emphasised the importance of skills development in supporting this transition, showcasing initiatives to equip professionals with the knowledge required for implementing and innovating within green procurement frameworks. Additionally, she introduced the New European Bauhaus Academy (NEBA) hub, highlighting its role in fostering education and collaboration to align sustainability and inclusivity in procurement practices. Access the full presentation [here](#).

Figure 35: Policies and Instrument panel during the Wood Policy and Innovation Conference.

Part III : Innovative building products and systems for resource efficient, circular construction

In this presentation, Liselotte De Ligne from University of Gent discussed the new [WoodStock Horizon project \(grant no. 101181021\)](#), which focuses on empowering the climate-smart, circular, and zero-waste use of underutilized wood from both forest resources and the building stock within the construction sector. The project aims to support the New European Bauhaus by promoting the reuse and sustainable management of wood, addressing the challenges of material scarcity and environmental impact. She highlighted how integrating circular economy principles into the construction industry can contribute to sustainable, climate-friendly building practices, aligning with the NEB's goals of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity. Access the full presentation [here](#).

Figure 36: Woodstock co-creation methodology

Part IV : The New European Bauhaus Academy: Up- and re-skilling the sector’s workforce with innovative training.

Wood Policy and Innovation Conference | Brussels, 7 November 2024 9

Session D

The New European Bauhaus Academy: Up- and re-skilling the sector’s workforce with innovative trainings

Hosted by Horizon projects [NEBA Alliance](#) and [digiNEB](#)

Session moderator: [Mike Burnard](#), University of Primorska & InnoRenew CoE

Time	Title, speaker		
15:30	Architectural education: beautiful, sustainable, together Roberto Cavallo , President European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE), Belgium & TU Delft, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, NL	pdf vid	
	NEB Academy: European Alliance for Innovative Training Hubs Andreja Kutnar , Director/Professor InnoRenew CoE & University of Primorska	pdf vid	
	Training of construction workers for the green transition (CoVE Habitable) Višnja Koščak , Manager for Internationalization Holzcluster Steiermark	pdf vid	
	The NEB Academy North Hub Camilla Berggren-Tarrodi , Architect and project manager Research Institute of Sweden (RISE)	pdf vid	
16:45	Closing of session		

The projects are funded under Horizon Europe.

Figure 37: NEB Academy parallel session programme.

- **Architectural education: beautiful, sustainable, together**

In this presentation, Roberto Cavallo from the European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE) discussed the role of architectural education in shaping the future of sustainable and inclusive design practices. He emphasised the need for architecture schools to integrate sustainability and circular economy principles into their curricula, preparing future architects to address the challenges of climate change, resource scarcity, and social inclusivity. He outlined various initiatives and collaborations aimed at evolving architectural education to align with the goals of the New European Bauhaus, stressing the importance of a holistic approach that combines design, technology, and social responsibility in shaping built environments. Access the full presentation [here](#).

- **NEB Academy: European Alliance for Innovative Training Hubs**

Andreja Kutnar presented the NEB Academy and highlighted the role of the NEBA Alliance in connecting stakeholders, developing educational resources, and supporting projects that align with NEB principles. By bridging gaps between academia, industry, and policy, the NEBA Alliance aims to accelerate the adoption of sustainable and people-centered practices in architecture and construction. Access the full presentation [here](#).

Digitalisation is one of the core elements of the NEB Academy, supporting its mission to promote education and collaboration around sustainable, inclusive design and construction practices. The platform will integrate digital educational materials to facilitate learning, project development, and the sharing of best practices among stakeholders. This aligns closely with the objectives of the digiNEB project, which provides a dedicated platform offering digital resources to enable the practical implementation of NEB principles. By leveraging digiNEB's tools, the NEB Academy enhances its capacity to train professionals and foster innovation, bridging the gap between theory and application in the pursuit of the New European Bauhaus vision.

- **Training of construction workers for the green transition**

Višnja Koščak's presentation from Holzcluster Steiermark focused on the HABITABLE project, which integrates New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles into creating sustainable and human-centered living environments. The project emphasises circular economy approaches, the use of bio-based materials, and innovative construction techniques to enhance environmental sustainability while fostering inclusivity and aesthetic value in urban development.

This approach aligns closely with digiNEB's goals of providing digital tools and platforms to support NEB principles. By facilitating collaboration and innovation, digiNEB can help projects like HABITABLE optimize resource use, improve stakeholder engagement, and scale their impact. The synergy between digital solutions and sustainable design underscores the potential of technology to advance NEB goals across Europe. Access the full presentation [here](#).

- **The NEB Academy North Hub**

The presentation by Camilla Berggren-Tarrodi from RISE focused on the North Hub's role in implementing the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles in the Nordic context. It highlighted how the hub connects stakeholders across disciplines to address regional challenges such as climate adaptation, sustainable

design, and inclusivity. Through case studies, the presentation demonstrated practical approaches to applying NEB principles, emphasizing collaboration and the integration of local cultural and environmental perspectives.

This aligns closely with digiNEB’s mission of providing digital tools and platforms to support NEB implementation. The North Hub’s emphasis on knowledge-sharing and stakeholder engagement mirrors digiNEB’s efforts to enable effective collaboration and foster innovation across NEB initiatives. By leveraging digital solutions, digiNEB can further support hubs like the North Hub in scaling their impact and addressing region-specific needs within the broader NEB framework. Access the full presentation [here](#).

Figure 38: NEB Academy stakeholders.

Part V : Networking Sessions

The coffee and lunch networking breaks provided a valuable opportunity to delve deeper into the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative. Participants engaged in discussions about its principles and practical applications, sharing insights and exploring collaborative opportunities. These informal exchanges also allowed attendees to address specific questions about the NEB, fostering a clearer understanding of its implementation to drive sustainability, inclusivity, and innovation across the wood sector. Additionally, digiNEB was highlighted as a platform offering multiple digital tools and resources to support the sector in adopting and operationalising NEB principles.

4.5. Sustainable places: Onboarding Research and Innovation

The Sustainable Places Conference is a platform for collaboration and innovation, bringing together a diverse network of experts working toward more sustainable environments. This annual event fosters dialogue across disciplines, uniting researchers, urban planners, building designers, technology developers, material manufacturers, utility providers, standardisation bodies, sociologists, economists, and end-users. In 2024, the conference was taking place from 23–25 September at the European Convention Center in Luxembourg. The event focuses on practical solutions and interdisciplinary collaboration to support greener, more resilient communities.

How are the New European Bauhaus Values and Working principles perceived and implemented in ongoing EU-funded R&D projects?

On September 24th, in Luxembourg, Nebula B4P hosted a workshop focused on the New European Bauhaus (NEB) in collaboration with digiNEB and the NEB Academy. The session aimed to raise awareness about the NEB among a diverse audience of built environment experts, **explore how NEB values are addressed in their respective R&D projects, and identify challenges to advancing the implementation of the NEB.** Adopting a participatory approach, the workshop divided participants into small working groups to foster discussion and brainstorming. Traditional tools such as paperboards and sticky notes were used to formally gather input. A summary of the discussions is provided below.

The participants and their professional background | Forty participants joined the physical session. A majority of them filled in the online poll that was proposed at the beginning of the session, in order to get an overview of the attendees' profiles and projects. The next diagrams respectively show the background of participants, and the R&D projects they were representing in the framework of the Sustainable Places Conference 2024.

Figure 39: Sustainable places workshop - background of participants

About the NEB Values

Value “Sustainable” | Participants discussed their practices about energy efficiency solutions and strategies (insulation, passive and active solutions); the design and use of biobased and low carbon material; the consideration of local value chains; the whole life cycle approach, circularity and reusability; and setup of communities of practices.

The main challenges identified relate to: the lack of standards and the insurance issues when considering reused and recycled material; the difficulty to implement citizen engagement measures and the potential reluctance of local public administrations to this regard; the conflicting objectives and criteria (budget vs sustainability); the need to provide evidence on the benefits of sustainability for all stakeholders of the value chain; the need for behavioural change and the related difficulty to change the mindsets in the construction industry.

Value “Beautiful” | Participants discussed the beauty aspect as a sense of cultural identity, belonging, quality of life and feeling good. Cultural heritage was discussed as an example of buildings that can provide a sense of belonging and identity. The market should be prepared to offer a wide range of products that can adequately support building heritage preservation while ensuring energy-efficient renovation. The sense of identity and belonging was also discussed considering social and cultural activities that bring together the community in a participatory movement. The buildings' history and their relationship with personal history create an emotional connection between people and places. This brought up the topic of the legacy of historical buildings and evolved to the question of the legacy of new buildings. How will future generations admire the new buildings of today?

The beauty concept can be vague and often subjective compared to sustainable and inclusive. The challenge mentioned is related to adapting new technologies while preserving the cultural heritage, combining functionality aspects with aesthetics providing visually pleasant solutions, and the difficulty of the construction sector and procurement procedures to embrace changes. It was noted that beauty can be a challenge when people are still fighting to survive. Therefore, beauty might be only achieved when no one is left behind.

Value “Inclusive” | Participants shared various strategies for fostering inclusivity in their projects. Key approaches included co-design and co-creation processes, tenant engagement in social housing, and gathering input from diverse stakeholders. Participants emphasized the importance of working in large, collaborative teams, using workshops and tools for stakeholder engagement, and promoting open knowledge sharing. Psychological research, worker training, and involving intermediaries between professionals and residents were also highlighted.

Several challenges were identified in implementing inclusivity in their projects. Key issues included digital inclusion and ensuring broad citizen participation, particularly among different age groups. Managing large information flows, balancing digital and physical engagement, and building trust were highlighted as difficulties. Divergent interests, prejudices, and lack of awareness also posed obstacles, alongside communication gaps between researchers and scientists. Additionally, challenges around participatory foresight and maintaining social trust were discussed.

About the NEB Working principles

Working principle “Transdisciplinary” | Participants agreed that consortia in European projects are more and more interdisciplinary, notably with the increasing integration of social sciences experts. The involvement of local stakeholder groups was clearly identified as a key success factor to ensure transdisciplinary. The concept of citizen science was also discussed.

The main challenge raised by the group was the language issue when dealing with interdisciplinarity, both inside and outside a consortium: indeed, the terms, but also the concepts and values behind them, differ between cultures and disciplines. Reaching a common understanding is an absolute prerequisite to effective co-creation. Also, initiating a co-design process across different pilot sites throughout Europe is challenging, due to different practices and habits of the local stakeholders, each pursuing their own local agenda.

Working principle “Multi-level engagement” | Participants discussed how this was addressed in their projects. They highlighted the integration of top-down and bottom-up approaches, the importance of considering multi-benefit concepts, and the effective use of personal networks. Organizational challenges at different levels were also noted, along with the need for a neutral space where stakeholders at local, regional, and global levels feel empowered to influence project outcomes.

The key issues identified included difficulties in replicating solutions across different levels of stakeholders, split incentives, and balancing mindset changes with organizational shifts. Conflicts arose from differing narratives and dynamic versus static project elements. Additionally, replication challenges were noted, with external inputs varying significantly across local, regional, and global levels, complicating the consistency of project outcomes.

Working principle “Participatory” | Participants discussed that the participatory approach can be achieved through active communication, collaborative research, and knowledge sharing. Participatory activities must be well organised with well-defined tasks for all people involved. Surveys, workshops, presentations, and interviews are tools to deliver this approach.

Excessive consultations, surveys, and interviews voluntarily might be a challenge in the participatory approach. The skillset, training, and political adjustments were also identified as a challenge in this environment.

What did we learn?

This workshop provided valuable insights into how the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles—sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics—are being applied in real-world projects. Drawing from the experiences of NEB demonstrators, participants identified both the progress made and the challenges that remain in operationalising these principles effectively.

The importance of local contexts, interdisciplinary collaboration, and participatory approaches was widely emphasised as critical to achieving alignment with NEB objectives. While sustainability is often well-represented, inclusivity and aesthetics were recognised as areas needing more focused integration and tailored strategies. Practical barriers such as funding constraints and the lack of common evaluation

metrics were also highlighted, alongside opportunities to enhance stakeholder engagement and drive innovation.

As a key takeaway, participants underscored the need for clearer frameworks and stronger alignment between NEB principles and EU policies to support broader implementation and lasting impact. These insights will inform the next steps in advancing the NEB’s mission and its contribution to a more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful Europe.

Figure 40: Discussions on NEB working principles during the Sustainable Places Conference

5. Onboarding Channel: REGIONS

5.1. Onboarding of regional governments by the digiNEB EAB

The **Digital Built Environment** event in Zagreb, held over two days on the 20th and 21st of September 2023, brought together representatives of the NEB Lighthouses, policymakers, educators, architects, and researchers to discuss the future directions of digital tools and strategies in the built environment. This was a key moment for engaging Croatian regional and national government stakeholders in NEB initiatives, fostering alignment between policy, practice, and education to advance sustainable, inclusive, and digitally-enabled solutions within the built environment.

Figure 41: Mia Roth-Čerina, digiNEB EAB and host of the Digital Built Environment workshop.

On the first day, the **Digital Built Environment: Tools, Projects, and Future Directions in Practice, Research, and Education** workshop, co-organised by **Mia Roth-Čerina** (Vice President for External Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, and digiNEB Advisory Board member), served as a platform to explore the integration of digital tools across scales and contexts. The discussions focused on identifying gaps and opportunities in practice, education, and research, while addressing critical questions such as:

- What digital tools and projects have already been deployed in architecture and the built environment?
- How do these tools address the diverse needs of professionals and user groups?
- Are current funding mechanisms aligned with the operational realities of researchers, educators, and practitioners?

Figure 42: Franklin van der Hoeven presenting the digiNEB project.

Figure 43: digiNEB visit to the 3LHD architectural offices.

The morning session, led by **Frank van der Hoeven** (TU Delft and digiNEB coordinator) and **Michela Magas** (Industry Commons Foundation and NEB High-Level Roundtable), focused on practice and research. Contributions included insights from:

- **Marko Dabrović** (3LHD) on VOLUM3, a digital platform for collaborative architectural workflows.
- **Uwe Kies** (Innovawood, online), who addressed innovation in digital tools for the wood industry.
- **Roberto Vdović** (Adriatic Green Lab), presenting on sustainability-driven digital initiatives.

The session culminated in a moderated discussion involving key stakeholders such as the Croatian Architects' Association and Zagreb Architects' Association. Moderators and participants examined how digital tools are being utilised across different scales and contexts, while also debating the role of licensing, open-source systems, and the alignment of funding opportunities.

The afternoon session shifted focus to **education and professional development**, led by **Mia Roth-Čerina** and **Roberto Cavallo** (European Association for Architectural Education). Contributions included:

- **Robert Loher** (Chamber of Architects) on continued professional development.
- **Damir Mance** discussing the integration of digital tools into architectural education.
- **Bojan Baletić** presenting insights from the CENTRINNO Horizon project on urban manufacturing and circular economy.
- **Roberto Vdović** (FabLab) promoting digital literacy through hands-on educational initiatives.

This session also featured discussions on the role of digitalisation in meeting SDGs, the challenges of remote teaching, and the future of architectural education in a digital age.

On the second day, the focus shifted to **policy meetings**, bringing together the NEB Head of Unit and Deputy Head of Unit, representatives from the Croatian Ministry of Culture, and the Croatian Society of Architects. These discussions aimed to align Croatian policy with NEB objectives, particularly in fostering sustainable and inclusive urban transformation. Key topics included:

- The strategic integration of NEB principles into national and regional policy frameworks.
- Strengthening collaboration between NEB Lighthouses, local government, and national authorities.
- Ensuring regional governments are onboarded effectively into NEB's broader initiatives.

The event, hosted at the Zagreb Architects' Association and involving both on-site and online participation, underscored the critical importance of collaboration between policymakers, practitioners, and educators. It provided a comprehensive exploration of how digitalisation and policy alignment can drive innovation in the built environment, ensuring that local and regional efforts resonate with the broader objectives of the New European Bauhaus. The discussions highlighted the need for scalable, context-sensitive solutions that address the unique needs of different user groups while promoting digital literacy, sustainability, and inclusivity.

5.2. Policy recommendations in the DigiNEB White Paper

As a comprehensive response to the European Commission's proposal of a potential NEB Mission and future NEB Facility, members of the digiNEB External Advisory Board, NEB Lighthouse and NEB Lab leaders, co-authored a White Paper including policy recommendations informed by hands-on experience of working with cities and regions.

The White Paper stressed the need to address systemic inequalities and promote pluralistic visions by challenging Eurocentric frameworks and fostering localised, grassroots innovations. It has been provided as an Annexe of deliverable D4.2.

Example recommendations:

- **Radical Inclusion:** Emphasising participation and equity in neighbourhood transformations, with co-design at the core to ensure accessibility and citizen ownership. This includes the adoption of "safer space" principles and accessibility mapping to foster greater cohesion and representation in urban and rural areas.
- **Integration of Creativity:** Leveraging cultural and artistic practices to foster democratic participation and enhance sustainability transitions. The White Paper calls for recognising the arts as a critical driver of innovation and collective future-building.
- **Digital Ecosystems:** Advocating for the use of community-driven digital systems to enable neighbourhoods to serve as testbeds for societal challenges. This recommendation underlines the importance of integrating culture and community in data-enabled environments.
- **Ecosystem Living:** Promoting beyond-human ecosystems to challenge traditional urban planning by harmonising human and natural environments.
- **Regenerative Practices:** Encouraging long-term research and collaborative experimentation to redefine value systems, prioritising dynamic and entangled relationships over extractive economies.
- **Policy Alignment:** The embedding of NEB values into existing European Green Deal missions, rather than creating separate frameworks, to ensure cohesive and impactful transitions.

5.3. Onboarding of Policy stakeholder groups

Another strategy for onboarding Early Adopters focuses on the European Regions and leverages background work on a Regional Innovation Model completed as part of NEB High Level Round Table activities during 2022 together with the European Committee of the Regions, in a collaboration with Commissioner Ferreira's Cohesion Funds and INTERREG Europe, as well as best practice from pioneering and early successes of NEB regional initiatives.

At the meeting of President von der Leyen with the NEB High level Round Table on the 28th of January 2022, Michela Magas announced a joint proposal developed together with the European Committee of the Regions, for scaling the results of NEB innovations from the ground up across the European regions. This proposal was voted to be included as part of the official CoR statement at their 149th Plenary.

Press Release:

<https://cor.europa.eu/en/news/Pages/voucher-scheme-planned-to-support-cities-and-regions.aspx>

CoR Statement on NEB:

<https://cor.europa.eu/en/our-work/Pages/OpinionTimeline.aspx?opId=CDR-5640-2021>

First alignment of EU initiatives:

On the 1st of March 2022 Magas succeeded in gathering together members of Commissioner Ferreira's team working on the implementation of Cohesion Funds, the Rapporteur and representatives of the Committee of the Regions, and all of the representatives of Interreg Europe, including representatives of Région Hauts-de-France and DG Grow. The objective was to present the voucher scheme idea and see how existing funding mechanisms could be effectively connected in order to scale NEB innovations from the ground up. This fruitful meeting has been logged in extended minutes that highlight many important positive statements about joint collaboration.

Figure 42 summarises the core concept: an ecosystemic approach to EU funds that sees an unprecedented joining of forces to create a large-scale value network and a multiplier effect.

Following this meeting, Interreg Europe confirmed that they wish to launch calls that would fund the scaling of the most promising innovations. Representatives of the EIC declared that they were interested in capturing scaled innovations that correspond with the EIC's objectives. The colleagues implementing the Technical Assistance instrument from the Cohesion Funds have confirmed that the proposal is well aligned with the Cohesion activities.

The Committee of the Regions identified a legal precedent for funding this proposal with the WiFi4EU voucher scheme, which was launched in 2018 by President Juncker.

Onboarding of policy stakeholder groups:

- On the 4th of March 2022, Magas presented this proposal to the Meeting of the Rapporteurs of European Parliament's Committee on Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE) and Culture and Education Committee (CULT) at the European Parliament.
- Following Magas's keynote at the "Europe Cooperates" conference that launched the new Interreg programme, many regional stakeholders enquired about the possibility of running NEB activities in this way. Getting regional stakeholders on board was generally deemed to be a challenge, so this was considered by Interreg a very positive outcome.

- On the 21st of April 2022, at the annual EU conference of the Culture and Creative Sector (ECIS22) introduced by the President and Commissioner Gabriel, after presentation of the proposal, multiple stakeholders enquired how they could help to make this proposal a reality.

Following the above interventions the joint proposal evolved through ongoing EC meetings and has been represented in Parliament by Marcus Ros Sempere MEP.

The Regional Innovation Model for scaling from the ground up aligns with the Pact for Skills and EU Research & Innovation agenda by:

- Creating an unprecedented upskilling platform and multiplier for EU R&I
- Allowing for a flood of technology transfer from EU research to be tested and implemented by communities on the ground
- Connecting EU research with regional challenges and concerns
- Creating an ecosystemic approach to R&I for the built environment
- Implementing a transition to comprehensive inclusion for R&I participation
- Stimulating a fast, simultaneous and coordinated triple transition
- Making scaling of ideas to the level of excellence visible, desirable and achievable, creating a mission-driven culture throughout Europe.

Figure 44: Concept for a Regional Innovation Model scaling the results of NEB co-creation from the EU regions developed by Member of NEB HLRT Michela Magas in collaboration with the EU Committee of the Regions

This scaling and strategic funding alignment concept, originally proposed prior to the digiNEB project, has become a central theme in the Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook described in 5.5 below.

5.4. Onboarding regional policy makers via the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook

Figure 45: Michela Magas and Jan Åman learning about the community urban plans for Duved, February 2023.

In order to onboard regional ecosystems as digiNEB Early Adopters, partners planned to create a **Regional Innovation Model Handbook** that will assist regional communities in implementing innovative processes on the ground according to NEB principles, and scaling them through strategic alignment of EU mechanisms.

The success of the digiNEB success story **Duved** project and the **Norrlands Model** methodologies suggest ways in which such community-led and locally-focused innovation models could be replicated and scaled across a variety of different regional ecosystems in line with the New European Bauhaus objectives. In light of this ambition, Jan Åman, co-founder of the Duved project, joined partner ICF to create a **Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook**, that would suggest a possible way to think about scaling the NEB sparks on the ground across the EU regions using a systemic approach.

The work was conducted in collaboration with sustainability designer Adam Davis, and with contributions and feedback by regional government officials involved in the above projects. It is aimed primarily as an inspiration for urban planners, architects and thinkers, and regional policy makers who wish to leverage regional ideas in sustainable ways.

Figure 46: Printed copies of the Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook for dissemination

The Handbook provides a collection of strategies and activities for communities in regional ecosystems that takes into account the unique characteristics of each location. It is intended for anyone who is interested in societal development and sustainability, including policymakers, urban planners, architects, designers, and community members. It provides a common starting point for place-based learning and community prototyping, and empowers local public servants, policy officers and community organisers to facilitate bottom-up action towards smarter societies and more sustainable local environments. It covers topics such as financial systems, democratic processes, working with people from different fields of knowledge, and the importance of considering sustainability, energy, mobility, new production systems, regenerative materials and retrofit building in societal planning.

The Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook was launched with the regional governor of the County of Västerbotten, city representatives and the Dean of the School of Architecture at the University of Umeå.

More about the launch event can be found in D4.2.

It has since been disseminated through the following channels:

- regional government: in Sweden: Stockholm, Västerbotten, Jämtland, Skåne; in Finland: Jämsä; in the UK: Pembrookshire.
- urban planners and architects network.
- industry interested in sustainability (e.g. IKEA, H&M, Vasakronan).
- with support from Bjørn Berge, Deputy Secretary General of the Council of Europe.

Figure 47: Printer's mockup of the RIM Handbook which features tested NEB methodologies

5.5. RIM Handbook

The Regional Innovation Model (RIM) Handbook builds on the legacy of the Early Adopter community, including examples and lessons from the NEB Lighthouse project methodologies, concepts from the NEB Labs, expertise from the digiNEB EAB, as well as publications and related expertise in policy development and community innovation facilitation by the JRC, Cohesion programme and the European Committee of the Regions.

Inspired by documented practice, papers, publications and results from the NEB activities, as well as contemporary and emerging digital tools relevant to or developed by the NEB community, the handbook addresses regional policymakers as change enablers – capable of galvanising diverse communities and leveraging digital technologies to create innovative, context-specific solutions. As facilitators, mentors, and collaborators, public administrators are encouraged to gather diverse and interdisciplinary communities to co-create innovative, context-specific solutions, prototypes, and inventions using the best practice methodologies presented, and encourage them to scale, taking regional expertise and ingenuity from their region to generate impacts across other regions.

The methods and tools presented enable onboarding, co-creation and community participatory design in response to globally significant and locally felt grand challenges. They suggest ways to work across domains with people from different fields of knowledge, and the importance of considering sustainability, energy, mobility, new production systems, regenerative materials and building retrofits in societal planning. They include strategies for leveraging digital technologies with local innovation communities

and ensuring positive societal impacts by embedding judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent (JUST) data practices to support the creation of AI for social good. They encourage evidence-based approaches to crafting policies responsive simultaneously to local needs and global trends, with knowledge of legal frameworks and the evolving technological environment.

Announced in a dedicated session at the JUST Industry Data Week at Linköping Science Park (see section 4.3.4 above), NEB lighthouses, labs and other NEB community members were invited to contribute their methodologies and best practices. The final version of the book will be available online as a public download on the digiNEB website, and dissemination of printed copies of the handbook are planned to take place in the final digiNEB event at Architecture House in Brussels on 17 December 2024.

6. Onboarding via video and social media

digiNEB successfully onboarded early adopters by leveraging social media and its website to create a dynamic and engaging ecosystem for outreach and interaction. Social media platforms were utilised to share impactful updates, showcase success stories, and promote events like NEB@CERN and JUST Industry Data Week, which highlighted the initiative’s tangible outcomes. Social media posts carried appealing content, including short videos and infographics, attracted attention and drove traffic to the digiNEB website. The website itself served as a comprehensive resource hub, featuring a well-organised repository of knowledge, including 53 videos and detailed project insights. Interactive elements like live event coverage and calls to action, such as subscribing to updates or joining early adopter programs, further streamlined stakeholder engagement. By maintaining consistent messaging and focusing on value-driven content, digiNEB fostered trust, expanded its community, and empowered stakeholders to actively contribute to its goals.

6.1. digiNEB community videos

Figure 48: JUST Industry Data Week video channel.

The digiNEB online strategy for onboarding early adopters has increasingly shifted in focus towards the production and distribution of video content, because of the medium’s effectiveness in delivering substantial, meaningful engagement with the NEB community. The video strategy creates connections between stakeholders, including NEB Lighthouses, NEB Lab projects, smart communities, EDIHs, and industrial domains.

To date, **a dedicated playlist from the JUST Data Labs contains 52 videos** from the week at the Linköping Science Park EDIH, while the **NEB@CERN event playlist hosts another 21 videos**, with a combined total of **over 1,600 views**. These videos offer in-depth insights and foster active participation within the broader community. This approach has proven far more effective than posts on platforms like Facebook and X, enabling knowledge exchange and content dissemination from in-person and hybrid events.

JUST Data playlist:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OHLdxyGlsGg&list=PLF3eM81pDgI1LwTbVwHnfcWLi8O5W69R9&index=2&ab_channel=MTFLabs

NEB@CERN playlist:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0dHr8UaPhxI&list=PLF3eM81pDgI2Fhdpn3chfnUVK1AfyW5yE&ab_channel=MTFLabs

Highlights videos have also been produced for other community events such as the 2024 **Wood4Bauhaus policy and Innovation Conference**, further extending the reach and impact of these gatherings. The video-led strategy provides an accessible, visually engaging, and knowledge-rich content that resonates with the community, and adds to the wealth of educational materials available to the NEB Academy.

Figure 49: NEB@CERN video channel.

6.2. KPIs

The impact of onboarding digiNEB Early Adopters through online media has been tracked and monitored, successfully surpassing planned KPIs. The number of Early Adopters has exceeded expectations, and the intensity of knowledge sharing has increased, driven by over 20 contributions at NEB@CERN and a repository of 53 videos produced during the JUST Industry Data Week. This has amplified engagement and fostered connections within the community, highlighting the value of more substantial content-driven strategies in achieving the initiative's goals.

KPI Description	KPI at M24	KPI achieved	Comments
Early Adopters	100	134	The full list of early adopters is available on request
Videos	24	83	Number of videos including CERN+JUST+W4B
Video views of Early Adopter content (KPI added in 2nd part of the project)	1000+	1600+	Video views to date. Updated figures will be reported in D5.4
Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	8 per month	223	Number of social media posts featuring Early Adopters' content
Marketing Campaigns	6	11	Number of marketing campaigns focused on Early Adopters

7. Conclusions

This document has presented the strategies for engaging Early Adopters within the digiNEB initiative and fostering their participation in advancing the digital implementation of the New European Bauhaus values of sustainability, inclusiveness, and aesthetics. These have included three major onboarding channels: academy, digital and EU regions, and have contributed to the creation of the NEB Academy, Digital Working Groups and the Regional Innovation Model.

The digiNEB Early Adopter Network has grown into a robust, multidisciplinary community that connects NEB projects, smart digital communities, policymakers and regional initiatives to drive transformative change through digital innovation.

By fostering a culture of collaboration, co-ownership, and interdisciplinarity, the digiNEB community has contributed to concepts and models that are scalable and replicable across domains and regions, and has paved the way for a resilient and inclusive European future.

- **Annexe 1: Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook**

The PDF of the printed version of the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook is attached as Annexe to this deliverable D3.4.

PROTOTYPE
FOR
AN
ECOSYSTEMIC
“HANDBOOK”

JAN ÅMAN & ADAM DAVIES WITH FRIENDS
IN THE NEW FUNCTION

ECO-SYSTEM // ECO-SYSTEMIC

The notion of an eco-system includes both the environment (or habitat) of a community, its inhabitants and their interconnections. Every part of the system – both environment and individuals, has a role to play for the system to function. The relationship and connections between different parts of the ecosystem are equally important and impossible to separate without causing disruption.

We often feel comfortable thinking about flora and fauna in this way but less often consider our own role and agency within different systems.

The term ecosystemic acknowledges the importance of each part of an eco-system and considers the specific relationships between its parts to become enabling for the whole system in a circular rather than linear manner.

PROTOTYPE FOR AN ECOSYSTEMIC “HANDBOOK”

PROTOTYPE

FOR

AN

ECOSYSTEMIC

“HANDBOOK”

**JAN ÅMAN & ADAM DAVIES WITH FRIENDS
IN THE NEW FUNCTION**

Walter Gropius Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922.

Remake/upcycle version of Walter Gropius
 Bauhaus Circle diagram from 1922
 for New European Bauhaus 2023
 by Jan Åman and Adam Davies (13.03.2023)

ECOSYSTEMIC CIRCLE DIAGRAM FROM BAUHAUS TO NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

This ecosystemic circle diagram is based on the Bauhaus circle diagram, designed by Walter Gropius in 1922.

Gropius designed it to structure the groundbreaking teachings at the Bauhaus School. Walter Gropius' circle can therefore also be a way to understand the principles of the era for which it was created.

Today things have changed, on all levels.

This is what this circle and "handbook" are all about new circumstances in a new era and how that has an effect on how we structure societal development to make it capable of handling the challenges of our time. This implies demanding solutions for many things – not least climate change and democracy.

New circumstances require new structures – which in turn lead to gradual system shifts.

This in order to enable us to organise smarter societies, to make our local environments more sustainable, more resilient, and not least to enable us to work, engage and make decisions in a way which is in line with the conditions of our time.

Returning to the Bauhaus circle diagram of 1922, and updating/upcycling it to our era is a way to visualise the needs, challenges and possibilities of today. The circle diagram can therefore be seen as a conceptual starting point for a new kind of "handbook" aiming to update and improve societal development. It can be seen as a checklist, perhaps a common starting point, for devising prototypes and taking action.

It is not a set of instructions to be followed step by step. On the contrary.

The ecosystemic circle shows that it is time to include several new layers for consideration in societal planning today. Things that had simply not been discovered in 1922. Climate change was not on the agenda back then. Today we need to include new processes, methods and structures – from

democracy to financial systems and learning to work with people with different areas of expertise/knowledge. As we will see, many layers have been added since 1922 and these have an affect on everything.

Important: The principles illustrated by the circle can never be applied in the same way in two different places, even if they are in the same country or the same region. It is not about industrial scaling – making the same again and again. It's about learning and improving systems. Systems need to be put in constant motion, developed and re-developed, updated and upcycled.

The one overarching aim is to accelerate the finding of solutions that adequately and fully address the challenges we now face as inhabitants of this planet. The time for that, as we all know, is running out.

It is a "handbook" made to spawn future handbooks, through participatory processes. But it does have one overarching aim: to accelerate the finding of solutions that adequately and fully address the challenges we now face as inhabitants of this planet. And the time for that, as we all know, is running out.

FROM CENTRALISED TO DECENTRALISED FROM SPECIALISED TO CONNECTED

INDUSTRIAL PRINCIPLE

ECOSYSTEMIC PRINCIPLE

In an era of digital connectivity, of creating efficiency by bringing together different disconnected fields of interest – an “ecosystemic” structure – a dialogue between different competencies will be generated. This is the possibility as well as the challenge. We simply need to work and communicate in a different way from that which we have been used to.

What is happening now is not that specialised knowledge is out of the picture. On the contrary, it is needed now more than ever. But today each specialised field of knowledge needs to be in much closer dialogue with other specialised fields of knowledge. Besides being knowledgeable in your own field, you also need to be able to take in information and ideas from other fields:

How does this have an effect on the civil servant?

How does this have an effect on business development?

How does this have an effect on politicians?

How does this have an effect on the local business?

How does this have an effect on the system of “specialists”?

How does this have an effect on citizens?

How does this have an effect on each and everyone of us?

How does this have an effect on communication?

How does this affect language?

Fields that used to function by themselves, for themselves, are becoming connected, out of necessity. Urgent necessity. On all levels, we are leaving silos and entering an ecosystemic development process. We simply have no other option.

This means that each and every one – private as well as public – needs to adjust to a new situation born of a technological shift.

The consequences of digitalisation have an effect on everything: how we live, work, act, organise and communicate.

It is not enough to add yet another specialised field or segment. It is not enough to add a new department of, say, sustainability or governance. The problem to solve is how specialised knowledge in one field can be implemented and integrated into other fields.

This means, for instance, that a building permit at a city planning department needs to be considered from a wider range of contents and values. To the architecture criteria and how the building blends into the city’s historical values are added, a number of other values, which include a quantity of additional information – on regenerative materials, retrofitting, sustainability, energy solutions, smart construction and much more.

This opens up for many things, as you will see. It has incredible potential. However for many reasons – production systems as well as the need for dialogue – the shift from centralised to decentralised/ecosystemic promotes a focus on local systems, on smaller-scale structures.

TO
PUT
IT
SIMPLY:
THE
LOCAL
IS
THE
FUTURE

CHALLENGES AND NEEDS LOCAL AND GLOBAL

Perhaps the most important difference with the Bauhaus diagram of 1922 is this outer circle: Challenges and needs, and their consideration from both a global and a local perspective.

The challenges and needs faced can be summed up in two words: Climate and Democracy.

This is a major change.

The idea behind the circle diagram is to show that climate – included in the outermost, perimetric circle – is a consideration that should be made an integrated part of each and every segment of each and every layer of the diagram, and not be a mere add-on. The UN Sustainable Development Goals, formulated during the World's Fair in Milan 2015, are a good guide to follow in this connection.

This means, following the 2023 circle diagram, that the idea of developing local societal processes based on sustainability can and should be part of all processes: the citizen's model, the governance system, the set-up or the setting up of segments, the problems to solve, the ecosystemic structure, as well as the action and doing.

Today the idea of a ZERO WASTE society is no longer a utopia. On the contrary. Over the past ten years plenty of examples of zero waste systems have been developed, within food systems, regenerative materials, design and architecture as well as infrastructure solutions, storage, circular economies and much more.

Starting a process in a local context – such as a neighbourhood or a village – will add a new value: the possibility of getting a variety of technological solutions and new companies to develop further side by side – by being put in dialogue with each other. This means the future of business will be developed on site, in neighbourhoods, in dialogue with entrepreneurs, with academic specialists, and together with the users, i.e. the citizens.

Technological development has given us a new *modus operandi* in which we all are used to being able to express our opinions and feelings directly, via our smartphones and computers.

It is not an easy transformation. According to the 2022 Democracy Index, published by The Economist, only 8% of the global population live in what are considered full democracies, whereas 36.9% live under authoritarian regimes. And with recent developments in some full democracies in mind, there is a clear need to find ways not only to strengthen democracy, but also to engage and involve the citizens in their own future – which in turn calls for ways to attract and engage people in taking part in societal development.

This brings us back to the local scale.

On a local, smaller scale, there is a greater potential for involving the citizens in a dialogue and getting them to engage with their own neighbourhood's future. There is a better chance of developing an ecosystemic structure on the local scale – of getting people to be part of developing and defining the future rather than just voting for a select few to represent them.

This local engagement might be called "ecosystemic democracy" or "deliberative democracy" – and in fact those two terms point out specific action points.

One – ecosystemic – that the citizens actually become more involved in the entire process.

The other – deliberative – that this requires a dialogue between the different partners in the structure.

LOCAL DEMOCRACY MODELS GOVERNANCE MODELS

The local has the opportunity to strengthen democracy, as well as to come to terms with climate issues. Global challenges meet local needs.

At the local level, try to generate interplay between the three main partners: the citizens, the public sphere, and businesses.

There are many possible solutions for developing this new role for democracy and governance – all in keeping with current systems and possibilities in each individual region and community. However in whatever way, they need to happen, and they need to be put into writing in order not to remain mere slogans.

If the citizens are not part of the development plan from the beginning, the old system will remain in place. This is nothing new. Throughout history it has been a classical battle. In Florence, in 1293, Giano Della Bella challenged the ruling families by introducing a system in which the city's different guilds were given a much bigger say in its development. The guilds' representatives were replaced every second month.

So, find a local, citizen-driven organisation, a non-profit. Or create one. Bring in the citizens and make it relevant.

Partner it with the public and private sectors.

Set up a structure with targets, with a vision, where everyone agrees on the end goal. Most likely a company, an Inc.

Then it is possible to create a successful process, and to match all the partners that are needed. And make them collaborate instead of the opposite.

As you will see, this is just the groundwork in realising the potential inherent in today's society, where academic structures are no longer confined to their towers of Babel in the city – and where the need to match finances with innovation and research is brought into dialogue with the actual doing.

THIS IS WHAT THE ECOSYSTEMIC CIRCLE IS ALL ABOUT

FINANCIAL MODELS BUSINESS MODELS

The ecosystemic circle heralds a shift from silos to connectivity. This could, in fact, be seen as a blockchain In Real Life. The centre is no longer the centre. The action (and the business) no longer comes from the centre, but from a decentralised connectivity. Instead of dividing decisions and money into different categories and systems, it suggests

the opposite. It starts from the bigger picture – the entire circle and all the content that goes into it – and thus opens for a completely different ballgame.

This has a huge impact on systems of financing and investing, in fact, on the entire world of business.

Decentralisation means that even large companies will have to remodel themselves in order to develop local business models with system scaling rather than product scaling. Mass production is a phenomenon of the past, but there will be other ways to scale in order to keep costs down.

The ecosystemic financial system is learning from the local process. It needs to take care of financial resources, make them efficient and make them sustainable. Investments – and the products coming out of investments – have a long term goal.

In both larger cities and local communities, business models are now being based on partnership use and multi-use to a much greater extent. The single-function approach has been challenged for some time.

Multi-use is simply about making the most of what you have. A kitchen can be used for public food preparation in the morning and for a restaurant cooking in the evening. A square in the city can be used for leisure and for temporary markets and to grow food – at the same time. A hotel can be a marketplace and an office as well. And so on.

This is about moving the financial system out into the local doing, to the action. It is about creating a context for investment. The next generation of investment funds will be smaller, local, and driven by AI – to learn from others, and never start with a blank canvas. This is about shifting innovation out of its dedicated silos and into an ecosystem in real life.

THE SET-UP

A new era requires a new set-up of which areas to cover and to instigate a real ecosystem. See it as a possible game plan. If you set things up in the right way, the wheel just might begin to turn, and people might just gradually get more and more accustomed

to an ecosystemic reality, where they do not in the first instance protect their position but exchange content, share experiences – and synergy can begin.

BE CO-CREATIVE

Societal development of today must be based on the reality that the era of silos is over, replaced by an interactive ecosystemic structure.

Knowledge and decisions are decentralised by bringing in other players, from citizens to expertise, to handle the complexity of today's society and the challenges that brings.

The real value is when co-creation is based on expertise from other fields than your own.

So – be even sharper and more precise within your own field. But bring in expertise from other fields, and always ask yourself: how can what I am about to do be done in a way that is smarter, leads to a more sustainable world, contributes to the future of the local community, and at the same time generates a new business model?

UNDERSTAND THE TECHNOLOGY SHIFT

Tech connects and makes ecosystems efficient. Plenty of solutions already exist in this area.

Use what you find and try it on a smaller scale, for instance on food systems or local construction systems. Test and trial. Connect different players. You will most probably see how the different players become more prosperous by being connected. That is how they generate new business. This pushes things forward.

Perhaps contributions to one local system will be implemented elsewhere, within a new context.

Use the tech-knowledge within your own organisation, as an integrated part of everything, and make it into a tool to create an ecosystem with the others you need to play with.

SEE EVERYTHING AS A LIFE-CYCLE

A new generation of chefs, designers and architects already has just about all the knowledge, the ingenuity, and the re-thinking that is needed. And through and with them comes a whole new generation of companies that have and/or are developing the solutions that are needed. Therefore you won't have to work in the dark or from a blank sheet of paper.

Looking at the next level towards the centre of the circle, we find a selection of problems

to solve. Apply the idea of the life-cycle on each and every segment. See it as yet another aspect that needs to be considered in all decisions and plans.

This will be key to developing solutions for the future. Also link it to financial models, accelerators and/or incubators. What this heading brings to the local community is a whole new business and innovation model. More on this below.

AN INCLUSIVE AND TENTATIVE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS IS KEY

The idea of an inclusive process is to deliver a sustainable process – able to produce long term results, and where the first steps are connected to the last. This means that whatever occurs as things begin to happen – be it collaborations with academia, with

schools, with construction companies etc – , everything should be integrated into the same development structure, the same ecosystemic structure, thus generating synergies, which means innovation and developing a community at the same time.

Ideally you should start with a process where the first step is to gather the players – i.e. the ecosystem, from citizens (most important!) to investors to the political system – and together formulate the why, the what and the how.

Spend time on this. Find a budget for it. It might take a few workshops. But this is the key moment, and it is not expensive. On the contrary – the small amount of money you spend here will save you money throughout the coming process. And this is really the

only money you need to start with. But you need to structure the process so that you can develop the financial process along the way.

Divide the initial ideas into different categories (take a look at the content development circle and you'll find a suggested initial checklist). Decide on initial temporary injection projects – projects that bring attraction, action and that craft a story, and gradually move on to bigger investments.

MAKE SURE YOU UPDATE THE DEMOCRATIC MODEL

The local community is the perfect starting point for developing a more up-to-date democratic model. Why now and not earlier? As stated above, because the industrial system had the idea of centralisation as a core principle. Post-industrial society is based on decentralisation to a large extent, thanks to developments in production and technology. This shift, which is well underway and developing rapidly, will take us back to a connected local starting point.

The core principle is to find a platform where the dialogue can begin, one which is not run by the political or the public structure, and not by the investors either, not even the

citizens – but by everyone together, probably mediated and/or curated by a partner without a stake in the outcome.

To maintain the integrity of the process there are many possible ways to create this initial interplay between the three major partners in societal development: the citizens, the political/public sector and businesses/investment.

CREATE A COMMUNITY

Communities are sometimes perceived as the equivalent of traditional grassroots or citizen-driven initiatives. There is nothing wrong with them, but the ecosystemic idea is based on connections between different players – from citizens to specialists, from finance to political system, from creatives and back to citizens. So things here are a bit more complex.

This is a new kind of community. Maybe even a new definition of a community – an "ecosystemic community".

The common principle is not just commonality but also difference – even more so, in fact. It is a community whose members are

different but have a common goal, or an idea of a common goal. The various partners in the community take on the responsibility for talking to the others, for maintaining a dialogue with partners that are unlike them. This is a different kind of responsibility.

The ecosystemic community is a community based on common interests but also on different skills and roles to play in the interactive game. Short-term business interests are not in charge, the politicians are not in charge, the grassroots are not in charge. Instead they are all dependent on each other.

MAKE SURE TO SET THE SITE

Invest in a large aerial photograph printed on a large canvas (like the ones used for advertising billboards). Roll it out on the floor. A print like this is strong enough to walk on (but be sure to take your shoes off first). It is strong enough to put imaginary houses or other new stuff on (this can be made from wood or any other material; the print is a bit like a very big Monopoly board). It is also strong enough to use over and over again.

Print it at a scale so that the photograph is large enough to really walk on and to give you the sensation of walking around in your own city or neighbourhood, and to allow you to play on it, like a computer game in real life.

If you do this right, everyone who lives in and works with what is in the photograph will immediately see things from a new perspective that opens their eyes and makes them smile. After a while, walking on it, seeing those personal connections, where you live, where others live, reminders of what you did here or there, where you went swimming, shopping or furtively kissing. Whether you are a child at school or a professional urban

planner, you will probably have the same kind of initial sensation and experience.

The workshop groups should be made up of people of different backgrounds, different age groups, different roles within the ecosystem. Mixing established players with students and locals with professionals usually brings results.

Analyse and decide what you can start on without too much of a hassle and too much of a budget, so that you get going and get people to see that these were not just words but deeds; they may be temporary projects, but define them in such a way that they really become a starting point for a bigger picture and story.

Define a sequence of actions, from small to big, and communicate them to everyone involved – if you get the citizens to join in there's a better chance you'll also convince the civil servants.

BEGIN WITH EDUCATION AND LOCAL KNOWLEDGE SYSTEMS

Involve children in the societal discussion. Children are amazing innovators because their ideas are not stuck in how things are usually done. They are not in the system yet, and their eyes and imagination are open – which means that their ideas can be, and usually are, a great way to discover new possibilities. So put them on the aerial photograph and you'll be sure to get food for thought.

The transformation to a digitalised, ecosystemic world, will have a huge impact on the role and possibilities of academia, which will no longer need to be isolated in its tower. In an ecosystemic world universities and higher education institutions, in order to keep up with where society is heading and to be involved with other partners, will have to function increasingly in the same way. For

example, testing things through prototyping, and learning in real life.

But also learning by being in touch with others, with other competencies, which means both citizens and expertise from other fields of knowledge. In order to make this happen, universities need to move out into society and drive the research in real life. This means developing in real life – where architects, engineers, financial specialists and citizens also meet.

That is when co-creation happens.

THE PROBLEMS TO SOLVE

A new set-up and a wider scope for both external factors (climate and democracy) require new types of solutions for old problems, simply because the content is different – and because that’s what the challenges and needs are telling us. But these old problems also need solutions

which are in dialogue with each other, in – yes, you know it by now – a way that could be described as ecosystemic. This layer of the ecosystemic circle diagram is a short guide for you to be able to start addressing, if not solving, these problems.

INFRASTRUCTURE/MOBILITY

Remind yourself that people do not like change that is too radical; their everyday life cannot be too affected – which means that if something is taken away it has to be replaced by something else.

Remind yourself that there are innovations capable of handling most problems that might occur.

In the countryside it is difficult to take away cars as a means of transport on a regional level, i.e. to places other than the one you live in.

Start with the idea of the local community and define the local centre.

Make a plan for how to radically reduce the amount of cars and transportation in the local centre. To do this you need to plan the infrastructure so that there are local hubs at all the access points to the local centre.

This is where you have car pools, garages, storage and community food services – these will play an important part in the local community.

Try to fill the local centres with creative life as well by adding studios for making and selling and trading.

Add smart local means of transportation (there are a huge number of innovative solutions for this; you should look at several platforms to find the ones that suit you).

What happens when you reduce traffic is that you open up for other activities, for complementary use of streets and public spaces.

Invite the local business and citizens to plan these activities.

FOOD SYSTEMS

Food is the ideal starting point for updated societal development and action structures.

Why? Because food systems are easy to understand, easy for everyone to see the problems with. Food is a basic human need, something that every human needs every single day to stay alive. Food is nature. Food never went well with the principles of industrialism. To say that food is cross-generational would be an understatement. And the food industry is in the midst of a radical transformation, as it must.

First of all, the core of the ecosystemic world is smart collaboration and interaction. It is a system where different entities which used to be in competition, or on opposite sides of the table, can see value created by collaboration of different kinds – in order to cut costs and share ideas, improving on the ideas by bringing other players, different expertise and experiences into the game.

That means: see the food system as a food system, not individual restaurants, kitchens, public food etc.

The key factor in this is the local context, the local community: it is the tool for sharing, creating value and inciting new business, at the same time as developing tools that will strengthen democracy.

Gather all the players, preferably on the large aerial photograph on the floor and start working out how you can define a local food system – where there are plots of land to use, where there are kitchens that can be used for multiple purposes. Don't forget to bring in the citizens from the beginning, because they are both users/customers and possible producers.

Do not forget to bring in digital tools. A contemporary local food system combines the artisanal with the digital in order to reach parallel goals: locally produced food that is healthier, more nutritious, and tastes better – and at the same time efficiently organised and cost-efficient through local collaborations.

Create a local production chain. This is not as difficult as it might seem. Find spots where you can grow food outdoors during the season and then decide whether it should be run by local restaurants or by the citizens. Whatever the solution, it will bring you local produce at low costs.

Create a local supply chain, where there are enough players with the same idea – again it's a bit like blockchain In Real Life. Create a local distribution chain, ideally where you connect individual citizens all the way to the

larger players, like the local grocery store – and aim at getting the large players on board. Create a local multi-use chain, with different uses of e.g. kitchens around the clock. This goes for restaurant kitchens as well as institutional kitchens (in schools, for the elderly, hospitals etc).

Aim at making the local school food only from local produce – if this is done in collaboration with restaurants it gives them extra income. Let the idea of learning through food systems and food production be an important part of the societal structure – again, there is the possibility that children at school will learn about food and pass that on to their parents.

Aim for a new food culture.

Aim for a zero waste society.

AFFORDABLE & SUSTAINABLE HOUSING

The development of affordable and sustainable housing is an issue that urgently needs to be solved. With rising costs for housing in larger cities, even prosperous cities face a big challenge. In order to maintain cities' diversity there is also a need to build less expensive housing, which could even be temporary. Put simply, there's a need for smart affordable housing to go alongside larger and more expensive buildings. Add-ons, rather than permanent and large-scale.

Set some very clear goals:

Zero waste, 100% regenerative impact.

Prototype different specific issues in the initial phase.

Begin with a dialogue with the citizens about what is needed in every area: housing, culture, people, social diversity, connections with existing housing etc.

Don't just build houses by themselves, but do so in parallel with developing the local ecosystem in several other areas, like food, infrastructure, habitat.

Co-create between the different players.

Select architects to synthesise the different specialities into a design.

Don't forget to bring in energy systems as an innovative force.

Set up a development test site where you gather material and explore what you can do with it.

Make it into a regenerative site, a regenerative lab.

Develop new upcycled materials.

Build a local assembly unit.

One way to start is through building permits for temporary buildings, which can accelerate the process.

AIM
FOR A
ZERO
WASTE
SOCIETY

A PUBLIC HABITAT/SPACE

In terms of habitat and public space this is a win-win situation. By starting the interplay between different functions, by focusing on local activities in the local community, you get a more vibrant habitat, more life in the city, and you also open huge possibilities for local business development.

As mentioned already, radically reduce vehicle traffic in selected central streets. This not only sets you on course towards a regenerative future, it also opens up the street for multiple uses.

The local community and local businesses will thus have an opportunity for additional business through temporary activities, such as markets, in the street – which also has the social effect of bringing people together and generating attraction and communication, as well as a sense of belonging.

As you will see in the next section, this is the point where you generate synergies by opening up the physical community – the objective is to generate synergies.

If you reduce traffic in the central areas you need to fulfil two things. One is to have garages and car pools at specific hubs close to the centre – removing cars entirely and all at once is going to create too much trouble, and by moving towards car pools you can update the cars.

The second thing you need is smart local transport. There are numerous innovative solutions out there, – test on a smaller scale before you decide, as needs vary depending on climate and other physical circumstances.

Also, take a look at storage and food storage, to see if that can be added to the hubs for cars and transport.

The potential for this will be different in different countries and contexts. Parks in cities, especially larger ones, are traditionally thought of as places of beauty, which is great. However by bringing in some ideas from more rural contexts, they can also be part of the local community's food production.

This is why the habitat has to begin with the people, the human beings living in the community, and be a tool for generating common interests and purposes – and thus a tool for democracy.

CONTENT DEVELOPMENT

THE SYNERGY SYSTEM

As you can see by reading through the chapters in this "handbook", all of the areas have one simple thing in common: inter-connecting. To try to bring about a kind of puzzle where the different pieces can start interacting, playing and creating value.

This is done through combining qualities from different areas of a local community. It is a game that brings about more lively cities, that paves the way for a more sustainable and regenerative world, but which also develops future local business.

We have lived in a world set on separating entities, segments and knowledge. A world of unconnected specialised fields of knowledge. We are now entering a world where difference is an enabler, not a limiter. We also need to move the world from centralised systems to decentralised local systems. And where the ecosystemic circle's many wheels are put into motion.

To bring things together in a mutual system, generating interaction between different parties, is to start a game of synergies – and to generate efficiency as well as local business opportunities. But most of all, it offers the opportunity of breathing life and engagement into a local community.

So, the first thing you need to spend time on and have a budget for is defining local possibilities and what you can actually achieve in order to generate an ecosystem that allows for future business while helping to create a regenerative world.

This needs a formal structure, maybe a corporation of a new kind, not just fancy words. All projects have to have that initial process of defining the necessary questions to reach innovative and sustainable results.

Define what, where, look for spots, get out on that aerial photograph. Define the process as well, define the vision.

Spend time on this, refine the ideas

THE CREATIVE & PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

Going local and ecosystemic with participation of citizens and the interplay between different players is a very different starting point than that in 1922. In 1922 the designer or the architect, the creator, was more in control of the entire process, as Gropius' circle diagram illustrates. At least that was the idea and the possibility.

In 2023 that kind of control is impossible. There are too many people, too much knowledge to bridge between players and industries. The co-creative part is a necessity, where you collect input from different sources, input which is vital also for the end result. It might be sustainability goals, it might be adapting to a local community and new businesses, it might be other aspects that will have a definite impact on the end result.

This gives the creative person a new role, initially as part of a participatory process, a process in which many others provide input towards what is to be designed or in some other way made into a creative statement. This role should be to be part of and lead the process, or to curate it. Which means bringing all the players together and injecting energy to get the most out of each and every one.

Involving the creatives early in the process is important. This might be local talent, and in fact should be, to some extent. But it can also be creative people from other parts of the world. Remember that most creative people are triggered by an interesting proposal and context. You can bring in anyone you want. But remember also that creative impact based on content development may be a key to the project's communicative effect.

That's why you always need to bring the creatives into the entire process, to share the vision and the context, which is the necessary challenge. They are there to solve problems and come up with solutions that no-one else thought of.

That's the beauty of it all.

THE FORMS OF CITIZEN'S PARTICIPATION / DEMOCRACY

Start local.

The local is the future.

Don't make it difficult, activate your own surroundings.

Invite the citizens to be part of creating the vision for the future of the neighbourhood.

The big vision – make sure all the players, including the citizens, feel responsible for the discussion as well as the process.

This means that all parties are there on equal terms.

Set in motion a process not only for a specific development, but long-term, in order for it to continue in the local community, and get the municipality to accept it and formalise it between the partners.

Again, add investment funds, and create local innovation and collaboration with academia, creating both self-respect and jobs.

By creating a circular economy you enter a circular democracy.

It is an ecosystemic democracy, a democracy based on interaction and action in the local community.

Think of everything as local, everything you need is there – it's not better from elsewhere.

Democracy will prosper through the creation of a local community.

Avoid making local democracy too fixated on the traditional political spectrum; try to find ways beyond opinion, based on activity.

Have circularity and zero waste as starting points, because that will get a lot of people involved.

Food is a tool, an important tool, for generating something that everyone can engage with.

Let people engage in the way that suits them – not everyone likes the same things.

Culture is a tool. Find out how the local culture might be integrated into the process.

Find a legal organisation form, such as a company, that brings in representatives from all sides – politics, business and citizens – and arrange a budget to run a flow workshop with the citizens.

Make sure that what comes out of the meetings is reality-checked and that it then can be done.

If you prototype you test by doing – testing under real-life conditions is deeds rather than words, and makes way for development.

Bring in the municipality to see how they can become a part of this and gradually develop new habits, so that civil servants become enablers.

It's an ecosystemic transformation that begins with the local, with the neighbourhood, and then can move upwards.

The core of ecosystemic development is democracy.

REGENERATIVE DEVELOPMENT

The perception of waste is now ready to be challenged and redefined, resulting in a reduction of unnecessary waste globally. This inherently highlights the value of identified material by-products – i.e. waste – from businesses, and how the utilisation of the by-product can contribute to the growth of the business in which it originated by offering other forms of revenue.

Our relationship to place plays a crucial role in restoring ecosystems and regenerating our communities. It is essential to listen to nature and take sustainable actions that benefit the environment, rather than exploit it. Choosing to listen to nature can help us restore ecosystems we're a part of – allowing our communities to thrive and grow. Designers can accelerate this process by changing the way we think about and put design into practice. And in doing that it is possible to create more sustainable and resilient communities, better equipped to handle the challenges of the future.

The utilisation of waste from commercial/public activities offers opportunities for businesses to reutilise the waste they produce and to generate further revenue streams as the burden of waste is eliminated and turned into regenerative materials.

This means that new local businesses will emerge as a result of a local community turning regenerative.

It is a means of engagement for the citizens and thus part of generating a stronger local democracy.

Regenerative systems also mean regenerative ideas, where ideas are continually developed and are iterative.

It is a way to open people's eyes and minds to look upon their own neighbourhood in a new way, as a place filled with inherent opportunities.

The idea of regenerative systems spans a broad range of disciplines from architecture and design to food systems, but also on a

human scale. From new business models to new engagement models, the local community will play a strong role in the development of regenerative systems. There will be a strong connection to the place in which materials are identified, regenerated and upcycled.

Each citizen has the opportunity to feel engaged as a contributor to the local development of sustainability and thus of becoming an integral partner of that location and contributing to its development, not just the extraction of resources (physical and social) from that area.

Regenerative systems seek to minimise and reduce the negative impacts and harm that our activities have on the environment and society. In their place they seek to create systems and processes that actively restore, regenerate and renew the natural environment and the society/cultural fabric of the communities that they serve.

Supply chains which are regenerative will always succeed since they are a constant source of materials. The regenerative system will be a core source for innovating the local community, to connect and to develop future business and resilience.

ESSENTIALLY:
START
WITH
ELIMINATING
THE
WORD WASTE
IT DOES
NOT EXIST IN
NATURE

RETROFIT DEVELOPMENT

Retrofitting is to take care of, develop and innovate existing buildings.

Instead of tearing buildings down, a key to the future, especially in denser areas, will be to invest in retrofitting existing buildings to make them more efficient and resilient. This means an effort to update and upcycle what we have – with much less damage to the existing city environment – and make what is already there more energy efficient, as well as enhancing the seismic resistance of existing structures. It will reduce the carbon footprint to reach a 100% regenerative goal.

Retrofitting is really to take care of what you already have by lowering energy costs, reducing maintenance requirements and creating value for those that already live in the building and the neighbourhood, so they can fit into the updated approach to zero waste. It will be a key for future societal development since it both keeps what is there and updates it to fit future and global needs. Working with existing systems and infrastructure to reduce their carbon footprint.

Retrofitting is truly ecosystemic since retrofitting projects add new equipment, tech or building systems in order to improve the building, i.e. they combine the old with the new, the knowledge from before with that of the future.

Buildings and developments can become more carbon neutral by improving the external systems such as transportation to and from the building. E.g. new bike paths or upgrading public transport connections. Thereby keeping traditions and skills alive, but making them contemporary to handle global challenges.

It is a holistic approach to support all stakeholders, to motivate and facilitate changes that can be delivered through participatory and community-driven practice, triggering a wave of action within communities, the country and even internationally.

Maximise by connecting with communities, networks (business and public sector) and third party organisations.

INVESTMENT/INCUBATOR SYSTEM

To accelerate the regenerative societal process, we have to create a shared digital simulation platform for planet Earth that encompasses a multitude of layers, touching on all aspects of the built environment. This platform should redefine how we share knowledge, design, co-create with end users, and optimise for performance, challenging people to solve problems together and rewarding them for their contributions. By co-creating the solutions, we can ensure a circular and fully regenerative future.

As part of this effort, we should also establish a seed investor and incubator setup, a fund focused solely on building businesses that will help us decarbonise human presence on planet Earth. This initiative will bring together the best minds and solutions to create collaborative, scalable solutions

that can be implemented to help decarbonise our industries.

This fund should provide the necessary resources and mentorship to help these businesses succeed and connect them with the world's leading investors to ensure that the best solutions can be prototyped and delivered at scale. To evaluate potential businesses, we need to develop a plan for monitoring and measuring the progress and impact of each one as well as providing feedback and guidance to help them refine and improve their products and services.

To validate each idea, we need to conduct a comprehensive review of the current research and patent landscape as well as an in-depth analysis of the potential impact each business could have.

We also need to assess the financials, business model, competitive landscape, and team behind each company. Furthermore, we should consider the broader environmental and social impact of the business and its potential to scale in the future.

To support each business, this fund should provide access to capital, mentors, advisors, and industry experts. It should also help each business to find ways to prototype their ideas at scale. Finally, the fund should create a network of other investors, entrepreneurs, and

industry experts who can provide support to the businesses they have invested in. We have to create a vibrant and sustainable ecosystem of entrepreneurs, investors, and innovators all working together to help decarbonise human presence on planet Earth.

By collaborating across industries, we can develop scalable solutions that will pave the way for a circular and fully regenerative future.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY / DATA TRANSFER & SHARING SYSTEM ECOSYSTEM SYNERGIES

To connect ideas and co-create solutions across industries, we need to agree on transparent open standards that enable us to share intellectual property (IP) and align incentives. Digital technology can also help us decarbonise our industries and move all flows of matter in a circular manner.

However, the current practice of IP transfer needs fundamental innovation to maximise spinoff success. The traditional model of technology transfer is not suitable for cofinancing research and teaching on a large scale, and patenting inventions is often costly and unprofitable overall. The traditional licensing model also does not fit knowledge-based spinoffs.

Virtual participation against assignment of IP rights has several advantages. It allows for easy transfer of IP rights to spinoffs, reducing transaction costs associated with traditional licensing models. It enables spinoffs to secure the necessary IP rights for their business operations without significant capital outflows in the start-up phase.

Finally, it facilitates the involvement of universities and research institutions in spinoff financing while cofinancing research and teaching. According to a report by the European Commission (2020), clear legal provisions are required to ensure that all parties understand their rights and obligations under the model.

To make this a reality, we have to align incentives and team up. Currently, only giant companies with many verticals under a single legal framework can explore synergies and discover efficiencies, but too often they lack the incentives and agility to drive innovation at scale. We need to build a sense of community that aligns our goals across industries, creates shared incentives, and assembles the world's best minds to drive innovation for a sustainable future.

Money is already moving towards sustainable solutions, and change is already happening. But we have to accelerate the process by building 1:1 prototypes and living laboratories all around the planet to test possible solutions, share the lessons learnt, and prepare the best solutions to scale.

Collaboration across different knowledge silos is obligatory to achieve a sustainable future. By aligning incentives, teaming up, and creating shared goals, we can build a sense of community that drives innovation for a regenerative human presence on planet Earth.

Let's connect ideas, co-create solutions, and accelerate the process towards a truly sustainable, regenerative future.

**ACTION
PROTOTYPE
DO**

ACTION

This is not what you do when everything else – all the circles surrounding the centre – is arranged. No, the action starts from the very beginning of the process. The very first glimpse of an idea is part of the action. All

that follows – which might be a process that takes ten years or more – will be part of the same action, prototype and doing. So you've already started.

PROTOTYPE

In industrial logic prototyping is done in laboratories or separate test units. When they're considered ready for the market, they are... put on the market, almost like coming from outer space instead of from within reality. If you want to produce relevance, establish the idea of working with prototyping as a means of moving forward. Prototype in real life. Prototype locally. Test, try and develop. Use the prototype. Live in it if it is a building. Be sure

to curate the process properly. And get a budget to set up the structure, where you need to create a collaboration between the different players: citizens, public and private. Testing and prototyping in real life is a way to generate continuous engagement, democracy and business opportunities. And a way to save money while developing something that can, and most probably will, be used in other places as well.

DO

Doing is believing. Believing is knowing what you're doing. To know why, what and how. To understand context. Knowing is also figuring out what you don't want to do – what is no longer relevant. And to do that is to figure

out what you want to achieve by considering all the values added through analysing the updated, ecosystemic, circle in all its layers, and then: do.

This is a handbook. It should be easy to read. It should be used. Like a handbook. So we left out the references in the text. However, it is a handbook based on 25 years of experience and as well on contributions from very many. It is based on numerous conversations with so many people that all have, in different ways and on different levels, contributed to the content of the handbook. It is based on extensive reading and research. A few of the texts are listed below. A couple of projects have been playing the role of case studies, such as the development of Duved and that of Norrlandsmodellerna in Umeå, both in Sweden. But the intention is that the results

can be developed in other ways in other countries. Some may think the handbook is simplifying things. Some may think it is too abstract. So, then, go ahead and make another version, that is the whole point. This is only a starting point. Not the end. The initial idea of a "handbook" came from Michela Magas. The concept of this handbook from Jan Åman and Adam Davies in search of the new function.

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